

Measurements of dilepton pairs from $c\bar{c}$ and $b\bar{b}$ in $p + p$ collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200\text{GeV}$ with PHENIX at RHIC

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Abstract

Dilepton channels serve as a great probe for the extraction of the total charm and bottom production cross sections in hadron-hadron collisions. Furthermore, these channels give insight into the heavy-flavor production mechanisms by which the quarks are formed. Using the PYTHIA8 simulation tool, the azimuthal angular correlations are observed over the $\mu\mu$, $e\mu$, and ee channels for $p + p$ events with $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV at RHIC. This analysis highlights the effects of multi-parton interactions (MPI), at RHIC energies, despite previous speculation of their insignificance.

Computations for the charm and bottom cross section were made based on the azimuthal angular correlations measurements. Charm cross sections were obtained for the $\mu\mu$, $e\mu$, and ee channels by scaling PYTHIA8 simulations, run with and without MPI. The resulting charm cross sections from each channel were combined using a two-step approach: inverse-variance weighting for statistical uncertainties and a Monte Carlo Gaussian construct for systematic uncertainties. The final combined charm cross sections were $\sigma_{c\bar{c}} = 524.1 \pm 44.8$ (stat) ± 92.7 (syst) μb (w MPI) and 560.1 ± 46.5 (stat) ± 104.3 (syst) μb (w/o MPI), consistent with previous RHIC measurements and NLO QCD predictions.

To extract the bottom cross section, we analyzed like-sign dimuon events, which provide a clean signal due to B^0 oscillations and minimal charm/Drell-Yan contamination. After generator level corrections and scaling to data yields, the bottom cross sections were determined to be $\sigma_{b\bar{b}} = 2.50 \pm 0.34$ (stat) ± 0.15 (syst) μb (w MPI) and 2.58 ± 0.35 (stat) ± 0.15 (syst) μb (w/o MPI). These values align well with previous RHIC results and lie within theoretical predictions from FONLL, MC@NLO, and POWHEG.

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1 Introduction

1.1 The Big Bang and the Quark Gluon Plasma

The *Big Bang Theory* suggests that the universe as it is today was once a highly compressed and hot point. Over the 14 billion-year lifespan of the universe, it has continued to expand and cool into the cosmos we see today.

The physics that governs the universe is best described by the Standard Model, a framework developed in the early 1970s that describes three of the four fundamental forces: electromagnetic, weak and strong interactions. The Standard Model further categorizes all known elementary particles, including the Higgs boson, whose discovery in 2013 at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) solidified the theorem, confirming the final missing component. The basis of these particle are shown in Figure 1[1].

Figure 1: Elementary particles of the Standard Model[1]

In the early moments after the Big Bang, it is theorized that these fundamental forces, alongside gravity, were unified into a single force, often referred to as the *Grand Unified Force*[2]. As the universe expanded and cooled, a series of phase transitions caused the forces to separate.

The first major separation is estimated to occur around 10^{-43} seconds after the Big Bang, where gravity split from the *Grand Unified Force*, leaving behind the electrostrong interaction. After 10^{-36} seconds, this interaction was further divided into the strong and electroweak forces [3]. As temperatures continued to cool, two major phase transitions are expected to occur. The first of which, is the *electroweak phase transition*, where the electromagnetic force is separated from the weak force. This further causes all fundamental particles to interact with the Higgs field. The second phase transition, considered the *nuclear matter phase transition*, is where the Quark Gluon Plasma transitions to hadrons. This occurs roughly $10\mu\text{s}$ after the electroweak phase transition.

1.1.1 Quark Gluon Plasma Formation

Before the nuclear matter phase transition, the universe existed as an ultra-hot, dense state of matter where quarks and gluons moved freely and unbound by the strong force. This state is often referred to as the Quark Gluon Plasma (QGP). As the system expands and cools, the energy density begins to fall below the hadronization threshold thus leading to recombination and hadron formation. As interactions settle, the system enters what is considered the freeze-out period. This can be separated into two freeze-out surfaces, the chemical freeze-out, where inelastic scatterings settle and particle yields are fixed, and kinetic freeze out, where elastic scatterings settle[4]. This can be observed in the schematic shown in Figure 2.

Today, physicists seek to better understand this state of matter, hence doing so by replicating the parameters and energy density of the Big Bang on a lower mass scale. By accelerating and colliding protons or heavy ions, such as gold (Au) and lead (Pb), to ultra-relativistic speeds, we can achieve energy density and temperatures that surpass the Quantum Chromodynamics deconfinement threshold. This in turn creates smaller Quark-Gluon Plasma instances, that we can consider "mini Big Bangs." With the use of large colliders such as the Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider (RHIC), at Brookhaven National Lab, or the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) at CERN, one can replicate these collisions and study the properties of QGP under controlled conditions with the use of complex detectors.

Figure 2: The progression of a heavy-ion collision plotted as a function of t and z with (right) and without (left) the formation of the QGP [4].

1.1.2 Quantum Chromodynamics

The QGP is often described using Quantum Chromodynamics(QCD), the fundamental theory that governs the strong interactions between quarks and gluons. QCD explains how quarks and gluons interact via the exchange of force-carrying bosons, or gluons. This non-Abelian gauge theory is based on the SU(3) color symmetry group, much different from its counterpart, Quantum Electrodynamics (QED), which follows the U(1) electromagnetic symmetry. The QCD Lagrangian that describes the interactions for quarks and gluons can be written as shown below:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{QCD}} = \sum_f \bar{\psi}_f (i\gamma^\mu D_\mu - m_f) \psi_f - \frac{1}{4} G_{\mu\nu}^a G^{a\mu\nu} \quad (1)$$

where:

- ψ_f represents the quark fields for different flavors f (e.g., up, down, strange, charm, bottom, top),
- m_f is the quark mass for flavor f ,
- $G_{\mu\nu}^a$ is the **gluon field strength tensor**,
- D_μ is the covariant derivative that includes gluon interactions,
- γ^μ are the Dirac gamma matrices.

The **gluon field strength tensor** is defined by the following:

$$G_{\mu\nu}^a = \partial_\mu A_\nu^a - \partial_\nu A_\mu^a + g f^{abc} A_\mu^b A_\nu^c \quad (2)$$

where:

- A_μ^a are the gluon fields (with eight color charge states),
- g is the strong coupling constant,
- f^{abc} are the SU(3) structure constants, responsible for gluon self-interaction.

Highlighting a key difference from QED, in QCD, gluons carry color charge and interact with each other in turn, leading to their highly non-linear nature.

1.1.3 Properties of Quantum Chromodynamics

Quantum Chromodynamics is known to exhibit two key properties. One of which is the concept of asymptotic freedom. At high energies, often related with short distances, the strong coupling constant α_s decreases, thus leading to quarks to behave similar to free particles.

The strong coupling constant is given by:

$$\alpha_s(Q^2) = \frac{12\pi}{(33 - 2n_f) \ln(Q^2/\Lambda_{\text{QCD}}^2)} \quad (3)$$

where:

- Q^2 is the momentum transfer, or energy scale,
- n_f is the number of quark flavors,
- Λ_{QCD} is the QCD scale parameter (~ 200 MeV).

At very high energies ($Q^2 \rightarrow \infty$), $\alpha_s \rightarrow 0$, thus quarks and gluons behave as quasi-free particles, leading to asymptotic freedom. On the other hand, at low energies (large distances), we have confinement. This property causes the strong force to strengthen as quarks get farther apart, causing them to be confined within hadrons.

The potential energy between a quark and an antiquark can be modeled as:

$$V(r) \approx -\frac{4}{3} \frac{\alpha_s}{r} + \sigma r \quad (4)$$

where:

- The first term represents the Coulomb-like interaction at short distances,
- The second term (linear term) represents the string tension ($\sigma \approx 1$ GeV/fm), which increases with distance.

A significant property of QCD can be highlighted with the above properties: At large distances ($r \gg 1\text{fm}$), the potential energy grows indefinitely. Hence, energies are so large that it becomes energetically favorable to create a new quark-antiquark pair, or meson. This property of confinement holds until the system reaches extremely high temperatures and energy densities, called the **Deconfinement Threshold**.

1.1.4 The Deconfinement Threshold

As the energy density and temperature of the system rise to levels found in the early universe the thermal energy in system achieves levels such that the strong interaction cannot hold quarks and gluons together as hadrons. The key mechanism behind this deconfinement is color screening, a phenomenon in which the effective force between color charge is reduced due to the presence of a dense medium of virtual particles. This can be visualized when two heavy nuclei collide at high energies thus leading to the decomposition of the nucleus into its quarks and gluons. At high temperatures, the system becomes polarized by the continuous production and annihilation of quark-antiquark pairs. These virtual particles serve to shield the color charge, thus reducing the range of the strong force. This screening effect can be described by the Debye mass (m_D), shown below in the potential equation:

$$V(r) \approx -\frac{4}{3} \frac{\alpha_s}{r} e^{-m_D r} + \sigma r \quad (5)$$

- Where $e^{-m_D r}$ represents the screening factor.
- In a QGP, the Debye mass grow as temperature increases ($m_D \sim gT$).

Eventually, this screening effect is so strong that the confining linear term is not significant leading to the deconfinement of quarks and gluons. This is analogous to the Debye screening in electromagnetism, where a charged particle in an ionized plasma attracts opposite charges, forming a shield around it, thus reducing the effective range of the Coulomb interaction.

The transition from confinement to deconfinement occurs at a critical temperature, T_c . Lattice QCD calculations estimate this to $T_c \approx 155 \text{ MeV} \sim 10^{12} \text{ K}$ [5] [6]. At this point, the system undergoes a phase transition, where quarks and gluons exist freely in the *Quark Gluon Plasma*.

1.1.5 Quark Gluon Plasma Probes

Since the QGP cannot be directly observed, its properties can be inferred from the measurable signatures that persist after the system cools and hadronizes. These signatures, or probes, can be distinguished into three main categories: electromagnetic probes, hard probes, and bulk observables. Each probes provides unique insights into different properties of the QGP, such as its temperature, opacity, elliptic flow, and phase transition dynamics. This section will focus on the discussion of these probes, focusing on the probes important to the RHIC collider and those used in this study.

1.2 Electromagnetic Probes

Electromagnetic (EM) probes serve as a tool for studying the QGP. Unlike hadrons, which undergo strong interactions and are affected by the evolution of the QGP, electromagnetic probes escape the QGP unscathed. Examples include direct photons and lepton pairs and these can give insights into the thermal properties of the QGP based on measurements such as their respective time of emission.

1.2.1 Direct Photons

Direct photons can be produced from several sources in high energy collisions. To begin, prompt photons, originating from initial hard scatterings can give insights on the initial-state QCD affects. These can come from the following scatterings: quark-gluon Compton scattering, quark-antiquark annihilation, and bremsstrahlung radiation off of an outgoing quark[7]. These can be seen in their respective Feynman diagrams provided in Figure 3. These photons dominate in the high transverse momentum (p_T), and are unaffected by the QGP. We can also observe the properties of decay photons and thermal photons, but these will be discussed in the *Dileptons* section. The relative yields (logarithmic) in of these types of photons with respect to the transverse momentum is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 3: Feynman diagrams of prompt photon production by a) quark-gluon Compton scattering, b) quark-anti-quark annihilation, and c) bremsstrahlung radiation off of an outgoing quark [7].

Figure 4: Sketch of the (logarithmic) yields vs transverse momentum from different photon sources[8].

1.2.2 Dileptons

Dileptons serve as an important probe for the QGP as we can draw conclusions on the physical processes that occurred by looking into the dileptons properties. Originating from electromagnetic interactions, these dileptons, e^+e^- and $\mu^+\mu^-$, are dominated by different sources in the different mass regions. We can associate the different mass regions and decays by observing the invariant mass of the product leptons. In the low mass region ($M_{\ell\ell} < 1\text{GeV}$), the decays of light vector mesons dominate such as ρ^0 , ω , and ϕ decays[8]. In the intermediate mass region, ($1\text{GeV} < M_{\ell\ell} < 3\text{GeV}$), the dominant source of lepton pairs comes from thermal radiation from the QGP, often coming from quark-antiquark annihilation, leading to a virtual photon and production of a lepton pair. This region is particularly significant as it can give insights to the temperature of the QGP due to the relatively "clean" signal here. In the high mass region ($M_{\ell\ell} > 3\text{GeV}$), we can find photons originating from hard scatterings that can then further decay to dilepton pairs. This region also

contains the Drell-Yan Process, which originates from a quark-antiquark annihilation, followed by a virtual photon or Z boson that will then produce a lepton pair (shown below).

$$q\bar{q} \longrightarrow \gamma^*/Z^* \longrightarrow e^+e^- \quad (6)$$

Figure 5: Feynman diagram for the production of a lepton pair via the Drell-Yan process [9]

Given the Drell-Yan interaction is unaffected by the QGP deconfinement, we can utilize this property to explore nuclear modification factors, hence comparing the yields in proton-proton (pp) collisions to nucleus-nucleus (AuAu) collisions. Furthermore, one can observe effects of the QGP formation on *quarkonium decays*, such as J/ψ and Υ decays. These are more sensitive to QGP effects such as color screening which causes their suppression during the QGP formation. The Drell-Yan interactions independence from these effects serves as a baseline for measuring yields of products and the properties of the QGP.

1.3 Hard Probes

Hard probes are characterized by their production of hard scatterings, or scatterings that are high in momentum transfer (greater than 500 MeV). Unlike soft probes, which emerge from low energy interactions and can be explained by non-perturbative QCD effects, hard probes can be described by perturbative methods. This allows for direct comparisons between experimental data and theoretical predictions. The production cross sections can be calculated using factorization theorems, which distinguish the contributions from parton distribution functions (PDFs), hard partonic interactions, and fragmentation functions.

We can separate hard probes into 3 categories: high p_T hadrons, jets and jet quenching, and heavy quarks and quarkonia. This paper will focus on the aspects of heavy quarks and quarkonia, which fall under the umbrella of heavy flavor production. Quarkonia refers to the various quark-antiquark bound states such as J/ψ and Υ . These are much more vulnerable to QGP effects and interactions. On the other hand, Open-Heavy Flavor refers to hadrons having atleast one heavy quark such as charm and bottom. These are less susceptible to the QGP effects.

1.3.1 Open Heavy Flavor Production

Among hard probes, open heavy flavor production plays a significant role in our understanding of QCD in the high energy regime. Specifically, heavy quarks, such as charm (c) and bottom/beauty (b) quarks are produced predominantly in the initial hard scattering due to the large mass and energy, Q^2 , required in the initial scattering. Because their masses are much larger than the QCD scale, their production is well described by perturbative QCD (pQCD), making theoretical comparisons feasible.

It is important to note that as heavy quarks traverse the QGP, they can interact with matter thus causing losses in energy due to collisions or radiation effects. These effects are commonly known as *hot nuclear matter effects*. Specific to the RHIC collider experiments, proton-proton collisions are not expected to produce a QGP due to the low multiplicity and energy scale. This differs in the case of heavy-ion collisions, where energy density is often suitable for the production of a QGP[9]. Due to the presence of the QGP in heavy-ion events, one can observe these hot nuclear matter effects and compare the measurable properties and yields to the baseline proton-proton collisions.

Other nuclear modifications can arise with the formation of the QGP, which are often referred to as *cold nuclear matter effects*. These nuclear modifications include energy loss of partons as they traverse nuclei and modifications of nuclear parton distribution functions in the nuclei. These effects are often observed in collisions involving a light and heavy ion such as proton-gold (p+Au) or proton-lead (p+Pb). Again, similar to p-p collisions, these collisions lack the energy density and quark density to consistently produce a QGP. This makes these collisions ideal for studying cold nuclear matter effects.

These relationships are specific to the RHIC, but parallels can be drawn to other collider experiments like the ones done at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC). At RHIC, several different collision species and center-of-mass energies (\sqrt{s}) have been used in its 23 years of operation from 2001 to 2024. These details can be seen in Figure 6. The specific experiments and detector descriptions will be discussed in the coming sections. This differs from the experiments at LHC, often holding higher multiplicity collisions with center-of-mass energies hovering 13TeV. Due to this large difference in center-of-mass energy, the high multiplicity allows for QGP formation for smaller systems, such as p-p collisions[10]. This allows comparisons to be drawn between the two experiments and different collision parameters to understand the working of the cold and hot nuclear matter effects.

RHIC energies, species combinations and luminosities (Run-1 to 24)

Figure 6: RHIC energies, species combinations and luminosities [11].

Often, heavy flavor production can be found in the early stages of the collision, but can still occur at later stages via processes such as gluon splitting. These processes that occur in the later stages of the collision are referred to as next-to-leading order (NLO) processes. We can find the participants of these NLO processes undergo effects of the medium and hence result in different properties. This sheds light on the importance in distinguishing between these next-to-leading order processes from their counter part, leading order (LO) processes.

1.3.2 Leading-Order (LO) Vs. Next-to-Leading Order (NLO) Processes

The production of heavy quarks is governed by perturbative QCD and is driven by three main mechanisms: pair creation, flavor excitation, and gluon splitting. These can be broken down into two categories: leading order processes and next-to-leading order processes. Leading order processes, consist of the simplest of interactions lowest in order of the coupling constant, scaling with α_s^2 . This is dominated by the instances of pair creation, which in its simplest form, comes from a gluon-gluon fusion or quark-antiquark scatterings[12]. These can be written as $gg \rightarrow Q\bar{Q}$ and $q\bar{q} \rightarrow Q\bar{Q}$ with their respective Feynman diagrams shown in Figure 7. Some key signatures are also attached to this form of production. Particularly, due to the kinematic constraints of these processes, the heavy quarks are produced in a back-to-back configuration, then leads the products to have a large angular separation.

Next-to-leading order contributions include additional processes that improve accuracy to overall cross sections calculations. These scale with the coupling constant on the order of α_s^3 . New kinematics emerges when we observe higher order process such as the flavor excitation and gluon splitting cases. In the case of flavor excitation, a pre-existing heavy quark in the nucleon is scattered into the final state via interactions with gluons or lighter quarks. These can be written as the following $gQ \rightarrow gQ$ (shown as (c) in Figure 7) and $qQ \rightarrow qQ$. Gluon splitting occurs when a high energy gluon decays into a quark-antiquark pair. In the low p_T range, this plays a crucial role as gluon density is the highest[12]. This differs from the quark-antiquark pair produced in pair

creation as the products are often produced co-linearly. By comparing angular correlations with these leading order and next-to-leading order processes, one can begin to unfold characteristics heavy flavor production and draw comparisons to pQCD calculations.

Figure 7: Examples of heavy-flavor production diagrams. (a,b) Leading order. (c) Pair creation (with gluon emission). (d) Flavor excitation. (e) Gluon splitting. (f) Events classified as gluon splitting but of flavor-excitation character. [12].

1.3.3 Distinguishing Pair Creation, Flavor Excitation, and Gluon Splitting

We can utilize several measurable components of a collision to observe the relationships for the the processes explained above. The different kinematic constraints of charm and bottom lead to dominance of different processes varying based on collision energy. Figure 1.3.3 shows the predicted charm and bottom cross sections and the relative contributions from pair creation, flavor excitation, and gluon splitting, based on pQCD calculations[12]. It is evident that in charm production, pair creation dominates across all collision energies whilst the NLO processes of flavor excitation and gluon splitting contribute less to the cross section. Gluon splitting further lacks in the lower \sqrt{s} range as it is less probable to generate a gluon with enough energy to produce charm-anticharm ($c\bar{c}$) pair. This is consistent with the case in bottom production. With the higher mass of the bottom quark is very improbable for a bottom-antibottom ($b\bar{b}$) pair be produced via gluon splitting. At high \sqrt{s} , gluon splitting's contributions to charm starts to become significant, but this doesn't hold for bottom. In the case of bottom production, at low \sqrt{s} , pair creation is probable as it is the lowest order process given the respective kinematic constraints. As the \sqrt{s} increases, we observe

an increase in flavor excitation contributions which is a direct consequence of the probability of finding a bottom quark on the mass shell increasing with the center-of-mass energy.

Figure 8: The predicted total (a) charm and (b) bottom cross sections for pp collisions as a function of the beam energy. The contributions from pair creation, flavor excitation, and gluon splitting are shown separately [12].

Other observables serve as key indicators for the production mechanism in a respective event. One can highlight key differences in the azimuthal opening angle, $\Delta\phi$ and transverse momentum relations to understand the kinematics associated with each process. As stated previously, we expect a much higher back-to-back correlation when observing pair creation instances. The next-to-leading order process will produce kinematics more co-linear which holds consistent with the previous findings as shown in Figure 9. Furthermore, we expect pair creation to peak at low Δp_T due to the back-to-back behavior and momentum conservation effects. The NLO processes are expected to recoil and experience much more broadening, This is due to the freedom of the incident particles energies, where they don't need to be as strongly correlated as is needed in pair creation. This is consistent with the results shown in Figure 9. This thesis replicates this form of study to further the investigations of these properties to gain a better understanding of heavy flavor production, as a probe.

Figure 9: Correlations between b and \bar{b} at 2 TeV $p\bar{p}$ collisions. Panel (d) shows the azimuthal opening angle $\Delta\phi = |\phi_b - \phi_{\bar{b}}|$ and panel (c) shows the difference in transverse momentum $\Delta p_T = |p_{T,b} - p_{T,\bar{b}}|$ [12].

1.3.4 $\mu\mu$ Pairs as a Probe

Utilizing lepton pairs as a probes serves as a great method to examine characteristic behavior of heavy flavor production. This thesis focuses on the study of lepton pairs to observe $c\bar{c}$ and $b\bar{b}$ decays and their relative contributions to lepton pair continuum. It is important to note, the relative contributions from $c\bar{c}$ and $b\bar{b}$ differ in different phase spaces and mass regions. Furthermore, we observe the respective contributions from un-like sign muons pairs, $\mu^+\mu^-$ and like sign muon pairs, $\mu^\pm\mu^\pm$. These tend to lie in forward or backward rapidity of the collisions due to the kinematic constraints required to produce muons and they're less affected by the collisional medium. This differs from electrons produced, often more affected by the medium and much lighter, hence found in mid-rapidity. This will play a key role in the selection processes to reduce background effects.

In this study, the focus on muons plays a significant role on highlighting the $c\bar{c}$ and $b\bar{b}$ contributions in specific mass regions alongside the heavy flavor processes contributions. Specifically, we can utilize like sign muons to distinguish the $c\bar{c}$ and $b\bar{b}$ signals. The $b\bar{b}$ decays are capable of producing a like sign $\mu\mu$ pair. This differs in the $c\bar{c}$ case as like sign signal is not present. This occurrence in $b\bar{b}$ is a direct consequence of B^0 and \bar{B}^0 meson oscillations. Due to the instability of these mesons, they can oscillate and thus lead to a like-sign pair. Furthermore, like-sign muons can further be produced from a combination of $B \rightarrow \mu$ and $B \rightarrow D \rightarrow \mu$. These processes can be seen below in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Like-sign muon pairs produced from a combination of $B \rightarrow \mu$ and $B \rightarrow D \rightarrow \mu$ (left) or from decays following $B^0 \bar{B}^0$ oscillations (right) [9]

1.3.5 Distinguishing $c\bar{c}$, $b\bar{b}$ and Drell-Yan for cross section measurements

When observing lepton production, we focus on the contributions from charm, bottom and Drell-Yan production. By separating the sources of different final state lepton pairs, one can begin to draw conclusions on the cross sections of these processes. Utilizing the like-sign dimuon background produced from $b\bar{b}$ decays we can gain insight on the bottom cross sectional measurements. Both $c\bar{c}$ decays and Drell-Yan processes do not contribute to the like-sign correlated lepton pairs. At mid-rapidity, the continuum of e^+e^- pairs is largely dominated by heavy flavor production from charm and bottom. Using the cross sectional measurements for bottom in the like-sign $\mu\mu$ pairs, one can perform a subtraction to gain an understanding of the charm cross section.

To isolate the contributions of the Drell-Yan process from the $c\bar{c}$ and $b\bar{b}$ decays, one must

recognize the mass regions at which each of these processes dominate. This is mainly governed by kinematical constraints. Due to the lower mass of the charm quark, 1.27GeV , the lepton production via $c\bar{c}$ decays tends to dominate the lower mass region from $1.25\text{GeV} - 2.5\text{GeV}$ [9]. Bottom quarks, with a mass of 4.18GeV , tend to dominate the higher mass region of $4.1\text{GeV} - 8.0\text{GeV}$. Due to its kinematical constraints and back-to-back nature, Drell-Yan production tends to dominate the high mass region in the dimuon spectra ($\gtrsim 6\text{GeV}$). Hence, utilizing the information from the like-sign dimuon spectra, we can feasibly separate the bottom and Drell-Yan contributions. These respective contributions can be related in the "cocktail" invariant mass plots shown in Figures 11 and 12. In Figure 11 we observe the $\mu^+\mu^-$ cocktail with the contributions from both open heavy flavor and quarkonium states. In contrast, Figure 12 shows a schematic view of the e^+e^- cocktail. It is important to note that the $D\bar{D}$ and $B\bar{B}$ correlate to the open-heavy flavor production originating from the $c\bar{c}$ and $b\bar{b}$ decays. We can clearly see the respective mass regions at which where these processes dominate using these figures.

Figure 11: Inclusive $\mu^+\mu^-$ pair mass distributions from p+p collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 200\text{ GeV}$ over the mass range from 0 to $15\text{ GeV}/c^2$. The inset shows the mass region below $4\text{ GeV}/c^2$ with more detail. Results are shown separately for the (a) south and (c) north muon arms. The data are compared to the cocktail of expected sources[9].

Figure 12: Schematic view of the e^+e^- pair mass distribution from p+p collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 200$ GeV.[13]

2 Scope and Outline of this Work

In this work, we seek to gain a better understanding of the inner workings of heavy-flavor production while examining the heavy-quark cumulative cross section measurements. Monte Carlo simulation tools have served as a great probe for these measurements. With the innovations made in PYTHIA8, this work focuses on studying the azimuthal correlations in various dilepton channels. These relationships will be observed and compared to findings from Run15 of the PHENIX experiment. Furthermore, seeking to gain a better understanding of heavy-flavor production mechanisms, this work will also highlight these relationships and relative contributions in different phase spaces.

Whilst probing heavy-flavor production, we further look to measure the charm and bottom cross section from the PYTHIA8 predictions. These will be compared to previous measurements (from the PHENIX and STAR experiments done at RHIC), alongside the theoretical predictions from pQCD and PYTHIA8. Examining the consistencies and inconsistencies will help to gauge the accuracy of PYTHIA8. PYTHIA8 further provides the inclusion of multi-parton interactions (MPI), which at RHIC energies has been speculated to have minimal impact on findings due to the smaller collisions (compared to the Large Hadron Collider). In this study, the effect of MPI will be examined to highlight the significance of their inclusion at RHIC energies.

2.1 Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider (RHIC)

RHIC, the first collider capable of producing heavy-ion collisions, is located at Brookhaven National Lab (BNL) in Upton, New York. RHIC was commissioned in the year 2000 and has served as a keystone to the research of the Quark Gluon Plasma and exploration of the spin structure of the proton. Through its years of operation, several experiments have been pioneered, such as the STAR (Solenoidal Tracker at RHIC), PHENIX (Pioneering High Energy Nuclear Interaction eXperiment) and sPHENIX experiments.

An aerial view of RHIC can be seen in Figure 13. The colored rings represent the paths traversed by the accelerated protons or heavy ions. Protons are first generated at the linear accelerator (LINAC), whilst heavy ions are produced at the Tandem Van de Graaf[9]. These protons or heavy ions are then injected into the Booster Synchrotron where they are then grouped into bunches and accelerated. From there, these boosted particles are injected into the Alternating Gradient Synchrotron (AGS) where they are further accelerated to $10 \text{ GeV}/c$ per nucleon. After leaving the AGS, the bunches are then injected into the two counter-rotating synchrotrons that are built into the 3.834 km (2.38 miles) underground ring. These two rings are commonly denoted as the blue ring and yellow ring, and house the respective beam-beam particles for the final collisions. Here, protons or heavy ions are accelerated up to $255 \text{ GeV}/c$ and $100 \text{ GeV}/c$ per nucleon for protons and heavy ions respectively.

Due to RHIC's versatility in producing different collision species and center-of-mass energies, it has produced significant research in the field. Many different collision species such as proton-proton, proton-Gold, Copper-Copper, and many others have been analyzed over its years of operation. During these 23 years of operation, spanning from 2001 to 2024, the different collision species and center-of-mass energies of the respective collisions can be found in Figure 6. This versatility has allowed physicists to study the generation of the QGP along with probing the different phenomena associated with it. This analysis will focus on the data taken by the PHENIX collaboration in Run 15, with a brief discussion of the upgrades made with sPHENIX and its respective strengths as a detector. Due to the focus on the simulation aspect in this work, the detector summaries for PHENIX and sPHENIX can be found in Appendices A and B respectively. These sections outline the inner workings of the detectors and provide a general understanding of particle identification, track reconstruction, and triggers in each.

Figure 13: An aerial view of the RHIC Collider

3 Simulation Frameworks

PYTHIA is a Monte Carlo event generator used to simulate high energy hadron-hadron collisions. By using a Monte Carlo approach, PYTHIA integrates the usage of probability distribution functions (PDFs) to simulate events, thus investigating properties of a collisions that could not be evaluated analytically. PYTHIA allows for simulations of different collision species ($p + p$, $p + Au$, $Au + Au$, and several others), observing key properties such as hard scatterings, parton showers, hadronization and the underlying event, in these collisions. In turn, physicists can use the insights provided by these simulations to put constraints on observables, simplifying the search for new physics[14].

In PYTHIA, the nature of an event is governed by the hardest process, followed by the multi-parton interactions (MPI). These are accurate to leading order, where the parton-shower evolution, including the initial- and final-state radiations (ISR and FSR) and scatterings have leading logarithmic accuracy. Event generation can be thought of as a three-step generation process. These are separated into the hardest process, the propagation of ISR and FSR, and fragmentation. To explain the general formulism of an event, an event begins when initial-state partons radiate and scatter inside the incoming projectiles in the form of ISRs. Upon collision, the partons of the two projectiles begin to interact, where the hardest process defines the event process, governed by the partonic cross section. During this, several other interactions, with a lower Q^2 can occur, namely MPIs. Partons leaving these hard processes will then radiate and scatter in the form of FSRs, until fragmentation and hadron decays conclude. A visualization of this is shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: The different sub-processes of a collision event shown schematically. The dark red blob represents the hard parton interaction, i.e. the process determining the nature of the event, from which initial-state showers (blue) and final-state showers (red) unfurl. The light green blobs correspond to the fragmentation processes of partons into hadrons and the dark green blobs to hadron decays or final-state hadrons. A second hard interaction is shown as a violet oval [14].

Within the PYTHIA framework, interactions with the detector are neglected as they are considered ideal and the particles are assumed to evolve in a vacuum. The previous analysis [9] utilized PYTHIA6 alongside POWHED and a leading order Monte Carlo generator to simulate the angular correlations in heavy-flavor production mechanisms. In this work, the analysis is shifted to PYTHIA8 to observe the improved accuracy and approximation of the new PDFs and MPI effects.

3.1 PYTHIA6

PYTHIA6[15] was developed in FORTRAN 77, later receiving its last major version of PHYTHIA6.4 in 2006, before the development moved to PYTHIA8. PYTHIA6 incorporated extensive QCD-based physics models, allowing its application and tuning for different collider experiments, such as the ones done at RHIC and LHC. In an attempt to simulate full high-energy events, PYTHIA6 was able to successfully capture initial hard scatterings and parton showers to the hadronization and final-state decays. Given the uprising understanding of MPI effects, PYTHIA6 used a combination of analytical calculations and phenomenological models to accurately represent event evolution. Although the successor, PYTHIA8, incorporated newer and more accurate modeling of

these MPIs, PYTHIA6 revolutionized the hadron-hadron simulation tools used and still serves as a great tool to understand the inner workings of the QGP.

PYTHIA6 featured the use of leading-order perturbative QCD calculations to model hard sub-processes. This included processes such as deep inelastic scattering (DIS), Drell-Yan production, heavy-flavor production, jet formation, electroweak boson production, and Higgs physics. The parton showering algorithms in PYTHIA6 are based on DGLAP (Dokshitzer-Gribov-Lipatov-Altarelli-Parisi) evolution equations. These describe the probabilities for a parton to branch out in the form of initial- and final-state radiations, occurring before and after the hard scattering, respectively. PYTHIA6 introduced the modeling of MPIs, or secondary scatterings within the same collision event. These play a crucial role in understanding the underlying event. The MPI model relied on some key components, one of which was a dependence on the impact parameter of the collision. The impact parameter, or transverse separation between the centers of the colliding protons (or nuclei), governs the probability of parton interactions. The impact parameter is directly related to the density of partons, hence controlling the likelihood for an MPI to occur. Furthermore, PYTHIA6 modeled MPIs using a semi-hard partonic cross section. With this formalism, softer (low p_T) scatterings occur more frequently in comparison to hard (high p_T) scatterings. To probe and tune these parameters, a minimum transverse momentum (p_T^{\min}) cutoff was introduced. This set the cutoff where soft (non-perturbative) interactions were separated from hard (perturbative) interactions. This cutoff is energy dependent as shown below:

$$p_T^{\min}(s) = p_{T0} \left(\frac{\sqrt{s}}{E_0} \right)^\delta \quad (7)$$

Here \sqrt{s} is the center-of-mass energy and p_{T0} is a tunable parameter that defines the minimum p_T at a reference collision energy. E_0 serves as a reference energy scale while δ is a tuning parameter that controls how the minimum transverse momentum scales with energy.

PYTHIA6 follows the Lund String Model to describe fragmentation. In the Lund String Model, color-connected partons form string-like structures. These string-like structures store potential energy as the separation between quark-antiquark (or gluon-gluon) pairs increases, until an energy threshold is met, where the string then breaks and a new quark-antiquark pair is formed. There also exist some specialized forms of hadronization embedded in PYTHIA6. This includes beam remnant hadronization and cluster hadronization. In beam remnant hadronization, remnants of the incoming hadrons must also hadronize and this is treated separately from the hard scatterings. Thus, some soft hadronization models are incorporated[15]. Cluster hadronization relies on color-singlet clusters that decay into hadrons. This allows for a better explanation of jet substructure.

With the intrinsics of PYTHIA6 explained, we can begin to truly understand the fine tunings and capabilities that come with it. In the previous dilepton heavy flavor analysis, PYTHIA6 was tuned to RHIC standard using "Tune A," with its specifications shown in Table 1. This tuning serves to control MPI frequency and several other parameters that differ between LHC and RHIC (due to PYTHIA's default tune catering to LHC).

3.2 PYTHIA8

As PYTHIA developers sought to produce a universal and integrable simulation software for high-energy collisions, they shifted from a Fortran built system to a C++ code. This change improved

Table 1: Parameters used in PYTHIA Tune A simulation[9].

Name	Setting	Description
MSEL	1	Turn on all QCD processes
MSTP(51)	7	CTEQ 5L, leading order PDF
PARP(67)	4.0	Set hard scattering scale μ^2
PARP(82)	2.0	Turn off p_T for multiparticle interactions
PARP(84)	0.4	Radius of core Gaussian matter
PARP(85)	0.9	Probability of color connection with neighbors
PARP(86)	0.95	Probability of closed loop color connections
PARP(89)	1800	Reference energy scale for p_T turn-off
PARP(90)	0.25	Energy dependence of p_T turn-off
PARP(91)	1.5	Primordial k_\perp Gaussian width
CKIN(3)	1.5	Minimum p_\perp cutoff

simulation efficiency, enabling better memory management and parallelization of object handling. Furthermore, this change allowed for seamless integration with analysis tools such as ROOT[16]. With the introduction of PYTHIA8, parton shower algorithms, fragmentation and hadronization models, and MPIs received some refinement and fine-tuning.

To begin, PYTHIA8's new parton shower model is based on transverse momentum ordering instead of the previous DGLAP evolution (ordered by Q^2). Instead of treating the emitted partons independently, PYTHIA8's parton showers use a dipole model, where radiation is seen between two color-connected partons (dipole). This leads to more accurate soft gluon coherence effects, thus a more realistic angular structure of the parton showers. In turn, the contributions from NLO processes are more accurately represented.

The MPI model in PYTHIA8 is much more sophisticated and tunable in comparison to the PYTHIA6 models. This is driven by its innate energy-dependence and impact parameter-dependence. As discussed in the *PYTHIA6* section, PYTHIA8 utilizes a similar construction of the p_T^{\min} threshold, but also incorporates an impact parameter dependence. Unlike the fixed Gaussian shape used in PYTHIA6, PYTHIA8 uses tunable proton profiles, which lead to more realistic central vs. peripheral collision modeling. PYTHIA8 further utilized dynamic color reconnection, rather than the basic string reconnection, to explain MPIs. Effectively, this causes the width and branching ratios of mesons to vary as a function of MPI frequency, thus broadening resonances.

with PYTHIA8, enhancements were made to the hadronization and fragmentation algorithms. Primarily, the string parameters in the Lund String Model were more tunable. This corrected issues that PYTHIA6 faced revolving around baryon production and low-mass string breaking. With improved PDFs and more precise string tension parameters, simulations began to align better with experimental data. Continuing, color reconnection directly affected the hadronization process. This dynamically adjusted baryon yields and the final-state particle distributions.

The main improvement of PYTHIA8 came from its ability to match and merge parton showers with fixed-order matrix elements. Matrix-element generators provide exact fixed order QCD calculations but do not model soft scatterings and emissions well. Simply combining the matrix elements and parton showers is not a feasible approach, as it leads to double counting. Hence, PYTHIA8 incorporates matching and merging algorithms to correct for the NLO processes and correctly compute cross-sectional values. Applying this to the simulations for RHIC, one can vi-

sualize once the first hard emission is generated correctly from the NLO matrix elements, then the subsequent soft scatterings and divergences are handled. Effectively, the LO parton showers govern the hardest interaction, while the NLO matrix elements correct for the higher-order processes such as gluon splitting and flavor excitation. We can truly begin to see how important these improvements are when observing the heavy-flavor production mechanisms at RHIC and the respective MPI effects. Below, in Table 2, is the PYTHIA8 tune used in this analysis (Detroit Tune).

Table 2: PYTHIA8 settings and tuning parameters2.

Setting	Default	New
PDF:pSet	13	17
MultipartonInteractions:ecmRef	7 TeV	200 GeV
MultipartonInteractions:bprofile	3	2

Tuning Parameter	Default	Range
MultipartonInteractions:pT0Ref	2.28 GeV	0.5–2.5 GeV
MultipartonInteractions:ecmPow	0.215	0.0–0.25
MultipartonInteractions:coreRadius	0.4	0.1–1.0
MultipartonInteractions:coreFraction	0.5	0.0–1.0
ColourReconnection:range	1.8	–9.0–0.0

4 Data Analysis and Results

4.1 Data set and Previous Results

The data set used in this study is from Run15, which consisted of $p + p$ collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 200$ GeV. This data was selected with the $\mu\mu$ pair trigger (MuIDLL1-2D) in coincidence with the MB trigger. The explicit track reconstruction and muon pair selection procedures used in the previous study can be found in the previous dimuon study [9].

In previous analysis, the azimuthal angle correlations ($\Delta\phi$) between quark and antiquark pairs were analyzed to distinguish between different heavy flavor production mechanisms. This azimuthal angle correlation was done for $c\bar{c}$ decays with unlike-sign dimuon pairs and for $b\bar{b}$ pairs with like-sign dimuons[17]. The individual selection of muons required a momentum of $p_\mu > 3.0$ GeV/c, and a rapidity within the range of $1.2 < |\eta_\mu| < 2.2$ (analogous to the forward and backward muon arm acceptances). It is important to note that in this analysis, the signals of the north and south arm were taken individually, then summed. These sums are then normalized to the data to achieve the final spectra. This means that both muons in a pair must come from the same muon arm, whether it would be the north or south arm respectively.

The purpose of the previous analysis was to understand the individual contributions of the different heavy-flavor production mechanisms. As discussed in Sections 1.3.2 and 1.3.3, we seek to observe the different kinematics associated with the different production mechanisms (pair creation, flavor excitation, and gluon splitting). With each process leaving distinct signatures, we can gain a better understanding of azimuthal correlation shapes to apply to experimental data. Furthermore, observing which process dominates within the given phase space and center-of-mass energy,

can also help draw conclusions on QGP formation and MPI effects. By studying these properties, inferences can be drawn to experimental expectations as well as improvements for the simulation software, to help better explain the data.

The Charmed decays were observed in the low-mass region, where backgrounds are low for charm production. The respective invariant mass region of the pair lied within bounds, $m_{\mu\mu} = 1.5 - 2.5 \text{ GeV}/c^2$. As seen in Figure 15, the $c\bar{c} \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$ decay is dominated by the flavor excitation process, a NLO process. The relative cross sections of these processes do agree with what we expect from QCD calculations as shown in Figure 8 for $\sqrt{s} = 200 \text{ GeV}$. We observe a low signal in gluon splitting due to the low probability of producing a heavy (c) quark on the mass shell via this process. Pair creation has a fair yield due to the more probable hard scattering to occur that generates a $c\bar{c}$ pair that can then decay to D mesons followed by the $\mu^+\mu^-$ pair. One inconsistency that can be highlighted here in this plot: despite the normalization to the data, a slight difference in the shape of the total trends can be seen. Furthermore, the cross sections calculated by PYTHIA6 and POWHEG (Positive Weight Hardest Emission Generator) are 0.314 mb and 0.343 mb respectively. These are much lower than experimental values observed in the $p + p$ run in 2005, $\sigma_{c\bar{c}} = 544 \pm 39(\text{stat}) \pm 142(\text{syst}) \pm 200(\text{model}) \mu\text{b}$ (where model is representative of the uncertainty due to extrapolation and theoretical assumptions) [18]. These inconsistencies shed light on some oversights and differences in models. This can be driven by the lack of NLO presence in PYTHIA6 and its struggles with MPI handling. With this, we apply this form of study with the newly updated PYTHIA8, looking into the developments in PDFs and heavy-flavor modeling.

Figure 15: The corrected $\mu\mu$ yield as a function of azimuthal opening angle from (a) charm and (b) bottom decays. The data are compared to the distributions calculated with POWHEG and PYTHIAv6. The model calculations are normalized to the data[9]. For PYTHIA the $\mu\mu$ pair yield is broken down into contributions from pair creation, flavor excitation, and gluon splitting.

Bottom decays were observed in the high-mass region, within the bounds $m_{\mu\mu} = 3.5 - 10.0$ GeV/c^2 . As stated earlier, we observe the relationship in the like-sign signal as $c\bar{c}$ and Drell-Yan do not contribute to the signal. It can be seen in Figure 15, the production via pair creation dominates the bottom production. The production via gluon splitting is significantly low at RHIC energies, as expected, due to the low probability of producing a high energy gluon that then splits to produce a $b\bar{b}$ pair on the mass shell. The relative processes agree with the expectations shown in Figure 8. The cross sections in the $b\bar{b}$ productions for PYTHIA6 and POWHEG are $3.59 \mu\text{b}$ and $3.94 \mu\text{b}$ respectively. Comparing to the $p + p$ run in 2005, $\sigma_{b\bar{b}} = 3.9 \pm 2.5(\text{stat})_{-2}^{+3}(\text{syst}) \mu\text{b}$, these values do fall within uncertainties. These consistencies highlights some key properties of $b\bar{b}$ decays, showing that the decays are well described up with the PYTHIA6 formalism. This can be a direct consequence to $b\bar{b}$'s unlikelyhood to appear in MPIs. Due to the large mass of bottom quarks, the energy required to produce a pair is often enough to be considered the hardest interaction at RHIC energies. This makes $b\bar{b}$ less susceptible to MPI effects. This is not the case for charm, as charm is much more likely to be produced via a secondary scattering.

The analysis proceeded to observe other final-state lepton relationships. After performing a background subtraction using the like-sign yield in $b\bar{b}$, two angular correlation relationships were observed for the production of $c\bar{c}$ with $b\bar{b}$ as shown in Figure 16,

To begin, the $\Delta\phi$ spectra for $e^\pm\mu^\mp$ was analyzed. The cuts applied to final-state electron were as follows: $p_{T,e} > 0.5 \text{ GeV}/c$, $|\eta| < 0.5$. The cuts applied to final-state muons were as follows: $p_{T,\mu} > 1.0 \text{ GeV}/c$, $1.4 < |\eta| < 2.1$. It is important to note that only forward rapidity muons were paired with midrapidity electrons. This is because the original analysis included a comparison to $d + Au$ collisions to observe cold nuclear matter effects [19]. This led to the isolation of forward rapidity muons as the statistics of backward rapidity muons was low in the $d + Au$ case. Observing the azimuthal correlation shown in Figure 16, we can see a peak at π . This peak highlights on the hard scatterings back-to-back nature. The broadening of the $c\bar{c} + b\bar{b}$ curve is driven by the abundance of flavor excitation, a NLO process. This effect is driven by the much higher cross section of charm quarks compared to bottom cross section (2 orders of magnitude). The curves do seem to agree with the shape of the data within uncertainties but to the lack of statistics the error bars are rather high. Reiterating from the previous plots, the cross section of charm continues to underestimate when compared to experimental values while bottom production remains well explained.

Lastly, an opening angle study was done for mid-rapidity electron-positron pairs. The respective cuts were as follows: $p_{T,e} > 0.2 \text{ GeV}/c$ and $|y_e| < 0.35$. Restricting the invariant mass of the pairs to lie within the $c\bar{c}$ mass range ($m_{ee} = 1.15 - 2.4 \text{ GeV}/c^2$) and the $b\bar{b}$ mass range ($m_{ee} = 4.1 - 8.0 \text{ GeV}/c^2$), allowed for the minimization of background. These two mass ranges represent the mass ranges in which the respective quarks dominate lepton production. Again, due to the abundance of charm relative to bottom, we find that flavor excitation dominates the spectra. Here, we also find more signal coming from gluon splitting as the kinematic constrain on the final state particles or not as demanding, and this is driven by the fact that we are recording mid-rapidity electrons and positrons. (Note: this analysis is done in the PHENIX central arm acceptance, which in turn requires $-0.55 < \phi_e < 0.95 \parallel 2.2 < \phi_e < 3.7$).

Figure 16: (a) Electron-muon azimuthal correlations from $c\bar{c}$ and $b\bar{b}$, (b) dielectron opening angle distributions from $c\bar{c}$ and $b\bar{b}$, compared to PYTHIA and POWHEG. The legends are shared among panels (a) and (b). For PYTHIA the yield is broken down into contributions from pair creation, flavor excitation, and gluon splitting.

By observing the different angular correlations of heavy-flavor production mechanisms, one can gain insight into the different kinematic constraints associated with the respective processes. This can assist in separation of charm and bottom decays as we gain more understanding of the trends of these production mechanisms, These studies serve to help physicists understand the decay mechanisms of charm and bottom quarks and to further our understanding of QCD. Most importantly, these relationships help test the hadronization and fragmentation models developed. By studying variations in the shapes of trends and the dominant heavy-flavor process, we can begin to understand if higher order processes are not accounted for in the calculations of the overall cross sections. This furthers the search for new physics and the need for more precise PDFs.

4.2 Strategy of Analysis

PYTHIA8 generation allows for the selection of different processes via the *HardQCD* and *SoftQCD* settings. *HardQCD* relies on high momentum perturbative QCD process whilst *SoftQCD* observes low momentum transfer interactions with non-perturbative effects. This plays an important role in the analysis as we seek the best representation of experimental findings. To observe the significance of these QCD processes one can measure the overall proton-proton cross sections. The cross section measured at RHIC, specifically for inelastic $p+p$ collisions has been calculated to $\sigma_{\text{inel}} = 42.07 \pm 0.20(\text{stat})_{-1.99}^{+2.05}(\text{lum}) \pm 0.40(\rho)_{-2.12}^{+2.07}(\text{full})$ mb, where the uncertainties are driven by statistical error, luminosity calculations, and the parameter, ρ , which represents the ratio of real to imaginary part in the forward elastic scattering amplitude[20]. To compare this cross section reasonably to the PYTHIA output, we must discern a reliable process selection for both *HardQCD* and *SoftQCD*. *SoftQCD* allows for the selection of strictly inelastic collisions, parallel to what we observe at RHIC. This refutes diffractive cases that often would not trigger the level 1 triggers such as the BBC trigger. In PYTHIA, *SoftQCD:inelastic* processes, when summed, generate a cross sectional value that hovers ~ 42.97 mb, which lies within the uncertainty of the values found in data. This provides a reasonable process selection that we can utilize in our simulation. On the other hand, *HardQCD* does not provide the option of selection of diffractive and non-diffractive states but allows for individual hard scattering selections. To best represent experimental parameter without restriction, it is ideal to run PYTHIA with the *HardQCD:all* setting, but this drastically overestimates the experimental cross section, with a value of ~ 92.65 mb. Thus, in this analysis, PYTHIA is tuned using the Detroit Tune, discussed in section 3.2, and using the *SoftQCD:inelastic* processes.

Although *SoftQCD* is dominated by low-momentum transfer processes, hard scatterings such as the ones observed in this analysis (pair creation, flavor excitation, and gluon splitting) can still be found. This is directly driven by PYTHIA8's MPI structure and impact-parameter-dependent partonic cross sections. Essentially, PYTHIA8 incorporates perturbative scatterings, given the kinematics of the collision justify the process. Under this construction, some doubt can be casted on the under-representation of these hard scatterings to data observables, but the individual contributions remain proportionally conserved. Hence, within this analysis, the yields are normalized to data, similar to previous analysis [9][17], to observe the individual contributions of the heavy flavor processes within the PYTHIA8 computation.

As stated in Section 3, PYTHIA event generation can be broken down into 3 main components: the generation of the hardest process, the propagation of ISRs and FSRs, and the parton-shower evolutions and fragmentation. To observe the different decays of $c\bar{c}$ and $b\bar{b}$ and the respective

heavy-flavor production mechanisms, we must identify the signatures present in the event displays.

4.2.1 Isolating $c\bar{c}$ and $b\bar{b}$ Decays

To begin, one must first understand the separation of charm and bottom decays. This can be done via tracking back through the particle ancestry starting from the final-state lepton, or via the propagation through the radiations and fragmentation of a parent quark. In this analysis, one starts with the final-state lepton that passes the respective cuts, then observing if it came from a charmed or bottom decay, and if so which heavy-flavor process it originated from.

This can be done by storing the parent particles of the lepton as we progress through its ancestry. This includes ascending to the different mesons and their respective excited states. Further up the tree, one can find fragmentation from quarks to mesons. Continuing up, the ISR and FSRs can be found, and lastly the hardest process is stored at beginning of the event. An example of an event listing can be found in Figure 17 [14]. In a given event, each particle is assigned an index, i , which is related to three step generation process explained above. Although the hard scattering is found at the beginning of the event listing, ISRs that led to production of the partons participating in the hardest process are named afterward despite occurring prior. Hence, it is key to utilize PYTHIA's status codes and ancestry classes to understand the unfolding of the event.

PYTHIA follows the Particle Data Group (PDG) for Monte Carlo simulations [1] to assign identification codes to all particles found in the event listings. Status codes are used to distinguish participants of decays, scatterings, and showers. Specifically, particles entering and leaving the hardest process (or MPI) are given status codes of -21 (-31) and -23 (-33) respectively. This serves as a method to distinguish between the MPI and hardest process. To continue, PYTHIA utilizes *mother and daughter indices* to track ancestry in an event. Upon an instance of Bremsstrahlung radiation, we can often find the same *mother 1 and mother 2* indices for a given particle. This helps to discern the ISR and FSR that occur within an event. Using these ideas, a system can be developed to delve into the ancestry and find the charm or bottom quark involved in the hardest process (or MPI).

PYTHIA Event Listing (complete event)							
no	id	name	status	mothers		daughters	
0	90	(system)	-11	0	0	0	0
1	2212	(p+)	-12	0	0	90	0
2	2212	(p+)	-12	0	0	91	0
3	21	(g)	-21	7	7	5	6
4	21	(g)	-21	8	0	5	6
5	4	(c)	-23	3	4	9	9
6	-4	(cbar)	-23	3	4	10	10
7	21	(g)	-42	12	0	3	3
8	21	(g)	-41	13	13	11	4
9	4	(c)	-44	5	5	14	14
10	-4	(cbar)	-44	6	6	15	15
11	21	(g)	-43	8	0	16	16
	:	:	:	:	:	:	:
122	1	(d)	-71	118	118	125	132
123	21	(g)	-71	110	110	125	132
124	-4	(cbar)	-71	93	93	125	132
	:	:	:	:	:	:	:
132	-423	(D*bar0)	-84	122	124	239	240
	:	:	:	:	:	:	:
239	-421	(Dbar0)	-91	132	0	290	292
	:	:	:	:	:	:	:
290	11	e-	91	239	0	0	0
291	-12	nu_cbar	91	239	0	0	0
292	321	K+	91	239	0	0	0

Figure 17: Example for an event listing in PYTHIA. Each particle that is generated in the simulation of a collision event appears in this event record with its properties: 'no' represents the particle index, 'id' the particle ID defined in the PDG Monte Carlo numbering scheme, 'name' the name of the particle and the columns 'mothers' and 'daughters' provide the particle indices of the first and last mother and daughter particles[14].

A key component to finding the charmed and bottom decays is the observation of the mesons that produced the final-state leptons. In our case, we look for 3 main mechanisms to produce final-state leptons: $D \rightarrow \mu/e$, $B \rightarrow \mu/e$, or $B \rightarrow D \rightarrow \mu/e$. In the case where a D meson is found in the ancestry, the decay is considered charmed unless a B meson is also found in the ancestry. This is a direct consequence of B mesons undergoing a weak decay causing the flavor change. Although the final-state lepton may come directly from a D meson, it originated from a bottom quark. Thus, this is considered a $b\bar{b}$ decay. If any B meson is found in the ancestry of the lepton, it is implied that it originated from a bottom decay. On the other hand, if a D meson is found with the absence of a B meson, it is implied that the decay is charmed.

4.2.2 Distinguishing Heavy-Flavor Production Mechanisms

Distinguishing between charm and bottom decays serves as half of the selection process. Further delving into the ancestry, one can gain an understanding of the heavy-flavor production mechanism that produced the quark and following lepton. Within the ancestry, we look for key signatures that separate the processes. These are discussed in depth in 8. Pair creation is defined by quark-antiquark annihilation or gluon-gluon fusion, represented by the following: $q\bar{q} \rightarrow c\bar{c}(b\bar{b})$ and $gg \rightarrow c\bar{c}(b\bar{b})$ (where $c\bar{c}$ and $b\bar{b}$ are interchangeable). Flavor excitation occurs when an initial state gluon splits into a quark-antiquark pair where one of which participates in a scattering with a gluon or light quark (up (u), down(d), or strange (s)). This is represented by $g + c \rightarrow g + c$ and $q + c \rightarrow q + c$ (the charm quark is interchangeable with an anticharm or both, bottom

and anti-bottom quarks). Lastly, gluon splitting occurs when a gluon, originating from an initial- or final-state radiation, produces a quark-antiquark pair which then does not take partake in any other subprocesses. In turn, it will directly hadronize without any other interactions. This can be represented by $g \rightarrow c\bar{c}$ (or $b\bar{b}$). Using the process discussed in the previous section, we can obtain the highest order charm or bottom quark, to distinguish whether it was involved in a pair creation, flavor excitation, or gluon splitting process. Moreover, this is done by observing the *mother* and *daughter* partons of the highest order charm (bottom).

4.2.3 Branching Ratio Restrictions

Due to the scarcity of these heavy-flavor production mechanisms in *SoftQCD*, we utilize a manipulation of branching ratios to improve statistics. PYTHIA8 allows for the manipulation of decay modes of mesons, while still conserving the individual ratios for each process. Hence, by restricting different meson decays we can in turn minimize the occurrence of pion decays and kaon decays, which often dominate over lepton production. With that, we can apply a weight to an event, based on the branching ratios of the respective leptons produced. Below is the calculation of the weight of an event based on the branching ratio corrections:

$$w = \frac{BR_{\text{sim}}}{BR_{\text{true}}} \quad (8)$$

where:

- BR_{sim} is the modified branching ratio used in the simulation.
- BR_{true} is the actual physical branching ratio of the decay.
- w is the weight applied to each final state lepton to correct for the branching ratio modifications.

To apply this formulism to an event, given a pair analysis is done, we can compute the weight of the event as the product of the individual weights:

$$w_{\text{event}} = w_{\ell_1} \cdot w_{\ell_2} = \left(\frac{BR_{\text{sim},1}}{BR_{\text{true},1}} \right) \times \left(\frac{BR_{\text{sim},2}}{BR_{\text{true},2}} \right). \quad (9)$$

The absolute normalization is then corrected to accommodate for these branching ratio modifications. The corrected yield due to this factor is shown below:

$$N_{\text{corrected}} = \frac{\sum_{\text{events}} w_{\text{event}}}{N_{\text{total}}} \quad (10)$$

where:

- $N_{\text{corrected}}$ is the corrected yield after applying the branching ratio weights.
- N_{total} is the total number of generated events in the simulation.
- $\sum_{\text{events}} w_{\text{event}}$ is the sum of all event weights.

4.2.4 Analyzing the Effects of MPIs at RHIC

To observe the effects of MPIs at RHIC energies, this analysis includes the yields for PYTHIA generation with and without MPIs. Under previous assumptions, MPIs were thought to have little to no effect at RHIC due to the lower multiplicity and center-of-mass energy. Although for low Q^2 interactions this may be the case, within this heavy-flavor analysis, the effects are presumed to be enhanced. To begin, due to the higher-order processes present as MPIs, we look to observe a broadening in angular correlations. Particularly, gluon splitting and flavor excitation occur more often as an MPI when compared to pair creation. In turn, the back-to-back nature of pair creation may be suppressed as flavor excitation and gluon-splitting contributions increase. To continue, cross section measurements will be greater for the incorporation of these higher-order processes. As we allow for MPIs to occur, the probability of finding a charm or bottom quark on the mass shell that later interacts in a scattering or decay increases. This effect is significantly higher for charm quarks as the kinematical constraints are more feasible given the lower mass. In turn, the prominence of these quarks will increase with MPIs, hence increasing the respective cross sections.

4.3 Angular Correlations in Heavy-Flavor Production Mechanisms Results

4.3.1 Normalization of PYTHIA8 Simulation

In order to understand and relate the yields of each part of this analysis, a set form of normalizations must be devised. In turn, the cross sections of both charm and bottom may be evaluated and then related to experimental values. To begin an absolute yield is first determined by taking the PYTHIA output and taking the ratio of favored events with relevant lepton pairs, N_{pair} to total events generated, N_{total} . This is then weighted using the formalism described in section 4.2.3. Due to the branching ratio manipulation used in the analysis the overall yields must be then reweighted to correct for this. This weighted yield is given by the following:

$$\text{Weighted Yield} = \frac{\sum_{\text{events}} w_{\text{event}}}{N_{\text{total}}} \quad (11)$$

The distribution is further divided by the bin width, $\Delta(\Delta\phi)$, to convert the yield to a differential yield. To keep the 4 analyses consistent a further correction factor, $\alpha_{rapidity}$, is used to correct for 1 unit of rapidity when necessary. This encompasses the corrections for 1 unit of rapidity when observing only forward rapidity muons in the $e\mu$ analysis as well as the correction for the ee analysis where the two electrons are found in mid-rapidity. This correction factor is specific for each analysis. The final normalization is given by the following:

$$\left. \frac{dN}{d\Delta\phi} \right|_{\text{per unit rapidity}} = \frac{1}{\Delta(\Delta\phi)} \times \left(\frac{\sum_{\text{events}} w_{\text{event}}}{N_{\text{total}}} \right) \times \alpha_{rapidity} \quad (12)$$

Upon obtaining an absolute normalization, the simulated spectra are then compared to the observed data spectra. Two forms of the simulation are run, one encompassing the multi-parton interactions (with MPIs) and one without the multi-parton interactions (w/o MPIs). These are then individually scaled to the data points to some scaling factor, β_{sim} , which is then used to compute the scaled cross sections. This will be discussed in greater depth in section 4.4.

4.3.2 Azimuthal Angle Correlations for $\mu^+\mu^-$ from $c\bar{c}$ Decays

The unlike sign $\mu\mu$ pair yield from $c\bar{c}$ in the mass region of 1.5 to 2.5 GeV/c^2 can be seen in Figure 18. This takes into account the yield from the southern and northern muon arms individually then combining them to form the total yield. Hence, both muons are either found in the northern arm, $1.2 < \eta < 2.2$, or in the southern arm, $-2.2 < \eta < -1.2$, respectively. The muons were further restricted to have a momentum, $p_\mu > 3.0 \text{ GeV}/c$. The mass region here was selected in a previous analysis, to isolate the charm contribution [9]. In the previous analysis, an iterative loop was used to determine the absolute contributions of charm, bottom, and Drell-Yan production. This is done using the like-sign signal from $b\bar{b}$ to isolate the bottom production and fit the cocktail mass spectra to what was previously observed in data. Conclusively, the mass regions for charm, bottom and Drell-Yan are given by $1.5 < m_{\mu^+\mu^-} < 2.5 \text{ GeV}/c^2$, $3.5 < m_{\mu^\pm\mu^\pm} < 10.0 \text{ GeV}/c^2$ and $4.8(11.2) < m_{\mu^+\mu^-} < 8.2(15.0) \text{ GeV}/c^2$ (where Drell-Yan has two respective mass regions).

The differential yield is then scaled to the data to observe shape differences and heavy-flavor contributions. Prior to scaling, the yields of the two forms of simulation differed by an approximate factor of 2, consistent with their difference in charm cross section. PYTHIA8 predicts a charm cross section in 4π of $594.7 \pm 1.7 \mu\text{b}(\text{stat})$ with MPIs and $356.8 \pm 1.0 \mu\text{b}(\text{stat})$. The scaling factors were calculated to $0.682 \pm 0.099(\text{stat}) \pm 0.088(\text{syst})$ and $1.250 \pm 0.180(\text{stat}) \pm 0.160(\text{syst})$ for with and without MPIs respectively. These values play a key role in determining the scaled charm cross section discussed in section 4.4.

Figure 18: The differential $\Delta\phi$ spectra for unlike-sign muon pairs from $c\bar{c}$ decays. The results from PYTHIA8 with(solid) and without(dotted) multi-parton interactions (MPIs) are scaled to data. The individual contributions from pair creation(PC), flavor excitation(FE), and gluon splitting(GS) are drawn in red, green, and blue respectively.

From Figure 18, it is evident that the shapes of the PYTHIA8 curves agree with data, consistent with the largely back-to-back nature of $c\bar{c}$ production. The handling of multi-parton interactions by PYTHIA8 allows for isolated handling of each MPI, leading to minimal broadening of the spectra when they're incorporated. Using its mechanism of matching and merging of the parton showers with the fixed-order matrix elements, PYTHIA8 serves to better explain NLO processes and cor-

rectly calculate cross sections. This is evident in the differences in the heavy-flavor contribution differences from PYTHIA6 15 to PYTHIA8 18. PYTHIA8 depicts a more severe dominance of flavor excitation in charm production whilst still obtaining reasonable values for the charm cross section.

4.3.3 Azimuthal Angle Correlations for $\mu^\pm\mu^\pm$ from $b\bar{b}$ Decays

Due to limitations in the softQCD generation in PYTHIA8, higher energy interaction such as $b\bar{b}$ decays are much less probable. Hence, to produce reliable statistics, we look to produce the like-sign spectra via hardQCD settings in PYTHIA8. Although hardQCD overshoots the proton-proton cross section, one can incorporate cross section measurements to relate hardQCD to softQCD given agreement in the phase space. To observe this relation, we observe the momentum, p_μ spectra of single muons from bottom decays.

To effectively relate *hardQCD:all* to *softQCD:inelastic*, one must understand the inner workings of each setting, which are described in depth in Section 4.2. Within the single muon analysis, one can scale the yields from hardQCD and softQCD by the respective cross sections to obtain a differential cross section vs momentum spectra. Essentially, with higher momenta, the region in phase space will be dominated by harder processes, thus smudging out the threshold separating softQCD from hardQCD. Due to softQCD's incorporation of harder processes, we can observe the harder processes, but at a much lower frequency. It is ideal to use hardQCD due to the efficiency of generation, but this requires agreement within the parameters used in the analysis. Hence, single muons originating from $b\bar{b}$ decays are observed for both HardQCD and SoftQCD, within forward rapidity, $1.2 < |\eta| < 2.2$. The normalization achieved involves weighing each event based on the branching ratio manipulations, then dividing by the total events, N_{total} . This is then scaled by the cross section of the respective PYTHIA setting to obtain a differential cross section measurement of the yield of muons. The normalization can be written as follows:

$$\frac{d\sigma}{dN} = \left(\frac{\sum_{\text{events}} w_{\text{event}}}{N_{\text{total}}} \right) \times \sigma_{\text{PYTHIA}} \quad (13)$$

Figure 19: The single muon momentum spectra scaled by cross section from $b\bar{b}$ decays. The results from PYTHIA8 are using the HardQCD:all(blue) and softQCD:inelastic(red) settings. The ratio of the two spectra are drawn below with a dotted line drawn at 1.0.

The results of the single muon momentum spectra, shown above in Figure 19, show agreement between SoftQCD and HardQCD in the respective phase space. This reinforces the idea that we are probing a phase space largely dominated by hard processes and that bottom production can be described by HardQCD quite well. Hence, we can confidently say that HardQCD within this phase space can describe PYTHIA output and is in line with SoftQCD. Thus this section of analysis, the $b\bar{b}$ like-sign analysis was done using the *HardQCD:all* setting and the corrections to the cross section will be taken into account in the calculations proceeding.

The like-sign $\mu\mu$ pair yield from $b\bar{b}$ in the mass region of 3.5 to 10.0 GeV/c^2 can be seen in Figure 20. The like-sign spectra are observed as they separate the bottom production from other signals that may contaminate the signal. Using the same formalism as before, the bottom production takes the separate yields of the northern and southern arms, then combines them to obtain the total yield. After the differential yield is obtained, it is then further reduced by a factor relating the HardQCD cross section to the SoftQCD cross section. Due to the higher innate cross section of HardQCD, the yield is corrected to be that of SoftQCD, which is representative of the $p + p$ inelastic cross section. This is then scaled to the data to observe shape differences and heavy-flavor contributions. Prior to scaling, the yields of the two forms of simulation differ minimally. This is largely due to bottom production being highly improbable in MPIs because of its highly demanding kinematic constraints. The larger mass of bottom, requires a much higher Q^2 of the interaction. This further leads to a dominance of pair creation as the main heavy-flavor production, producing a much more back-to-back correlation in $b\bar{b}$ decays. PYTHIA8 predicts a bottom cross section in 4π of $1.458 \pm 0.0081 \mu\text{b}(\text{stat})$ with MPIs and $1.458 \pm 0.0076 \mu\text{b}(\text{stat})$. The scaling factors were calculated to $3.78 \pm 0.52(\text{stat}) \pm 0.23(\text{syst})$ and $3.90 \pm 0.53(\text{stat}) \pm 0.23(\text{syst})$ for with and without MPIs respectively. These values play a key role in determining the scaled bottom cross section discussed in section 4.5.1.

Figure 20: The differential $\Delta\phi$ spectra for like-sign muon pairs from $b\bar{b}$ decays. The results from PYTHIA8 with(solid) and without(dotted) multi-parton interactions (MPIs) are scaled to data. The individual contributions from pair creation(PC), flavor excitation(FE), and gluon splitting(GS) are drawn in red, green, and blue respectively.

From Figure 20, one can observe a slight broadening in the spectra within the PYTHIA8 simulations. This may be a direct consequence of manipulating the D meson branching ratios. Particularly, by tuning the D meson decays to produce only muons, there can be a slight broadening in the spectra. Due to the corrections made to account for this, the yields will remain consistent, but with the increase in lepton production from D mesons, an enhancement of charmed decays occurs. Because B mesons can decay to D mesons and subsequently a muon, these events can produce a lower $\Delta\phi$, where this type of event would often be unlikely. This can in turn smear the $\Delta\phi$ spectra as shown in Figure 20.

4.3.4 Azimuthal Angle Correlations for $e^\pm\mu^\mp$ from $c\bar{c} + b\bar{b}$ Decays

The $e^\pm\mu^\mp$ pair yield from $c\bar{c} + b\bar{b}$ can be seen in Figure 21. For this analysis, electrons were taken in mid-rapidity, where $|\eta_e| < 0.5$, and with a transverse momentum of $p_{T,e} > 0.5\text{GeV}/c$. The muons were selected with transverse momentum, $p_{T,\mu} > 1.0\text{GeV}/c$ and within a rapidity region of the northern arm, with $1.4 < \eta < 2.1$. This rapidity coverage is later corrected for 1 unit of rapidity using the normalization described in Section 4.3.1. The differential yield obtained after normalization is then scaled to the data to observe shape differences and heavy-flavor contributions. The scaling factors were calculated to $5.077 \pm 2.28(stat) \pm 2.08(syst)$ and $6.57 \pm 2.91(stat) \pm 2.59(syst)$ for with and without MPIs respectively. These values play a key role in determining the scaled cross sections discussed in Section 4.4.

Figure 21: The differential $\Delta\phi$ spectra for un-like sign $e\mu$ pairs from $c\bar{c} + b\bar{b}$ decays. The results from PYTHIA8 with(solid) and without(dotted) multi-parton interactions (MPIs) are scaled to data. The individual contributions from pair creation(PC), flavor excitation(FE), and gluon splitting(GS) are drawn in red, green, and blue respectively.

Despite the large uncertainties in the data, Figure 21 shows a peak in $\Delta\phi$ at π , thus pointing to back-to-back production. This emphasizes the dominance of pair creation at $\Delta\phi = \pi$. Although this analysis includes decays from both $c\bar{c}$ and $b\bar{b}$, charm will dominate the spectra due to its much larger cross section and less demanding kinematic constraints. Thus, we expect to see effects of charmed decays and the increase in NLO processes when compared to the previous analysis of Figure 16 [9]. In the simulated spectra from PYTHIA8 shows a broadening and a less severe dip at $\Delta\phi = 0$. This broadening/smearing can be a direct consequence of the D meson branching ratio manipulation discussed in the previous section, as well as effects of NLO processes. As discussed in the like-sign $\mu\mu$ analysis, a smearing effect can be seen driven by the surplus of lepton production from D mesons. This can lead to enhanced low $\Delta\phi$ statistics, causing broadening in the spectra. Furthermore, charm, being dominated by NLO processes, can further lead to broadening. Within the unlike-sign $\mu\mu$ analysis we found a more dominant signal from flavor excitation. Inately, flavor excitation, generates a flatter azimuthal angle distribution, hence with its abundance in charmed decays, one may find some of these effects in the azimuthal angle correlations. Despite this, within the large uncertainty bands, PYTHIA8, can still suitably depict the angular correlations for the $e\mu$ spectra, shedding more insight on the heavy-flavor production mechanisms and how they act in different phase spaces.

4.3.5 Opening Angle Correlations for $e^\pm e^\mp$ from $c\bar{c} + b\bar{b}$ Decays

To complete the analysis, we observe the opening angle correlations at mid-rapidity for electron-positron pairs. Electrons (or positrons) are selected with a minimum transverse momentum, $p_{T,e} > 0.2\text{GeV}/c$, and such that they fall in mid-rapidity, $|y_e| < 0.35$. Furthermore, the final-state leptons are selected in simulation such that they would lie within the PHENIX central arm acceptance. This takes into account the corrections due to the magnetic field and the track reconstruction, ensuring

that the particles fall within the acceptance of the central arms [21]. The mass regions for this analysis were taken from the finding of the cocktail invariant mass spectra done in the previous analysis [9]. The fitting parameters were derived in the previous analysis such that the regions of least background for charm and bottom were discerned. These were found to $1.5 < m_{ee} < 2.5 \text{ GeV}/c^2$ and $4.1 < m_{ee} < 8.0 \text{ GeV}/c^2$ for charm and bottom respectively. The mass region for bottom here differs from the like-sign analysis because of a more restrictive measurement that may be contaminated by the Drell-Yan signal. In the case of the like-sign spectra, Drell-Yan production does not contribute to the signal, and hence we take a larger mass region.

Rapidity coverage of the central arms cover $|y_e| < 0.35$, when achieving a proper normalization, this must be corrected for a factor of 1, leading to a correction values, $\alpha_{rapidity} = 1/0.49 \approx 2.04$. The differential yield obtained after normalization is then scaled to the data to observe shape differences and heavy-flavor contributions. The scaling factors were calculated to $1.15 \pm 0.12(stat) \pm 0.32(syst)$ and $1.90 \pm 0.19(stat) \pm 0.54(syst)$ for with and without MPIs respectively. These are further discussed in Section 4.4.

Figure 22: The differential opening angle, θ^{op} spectra for un-like sign ee pairs from $c\bar{c} + b\bar{b}$ decays. The results from PYTHIA8 with(solid) and without(dotted) multi-parton interactions (MPIs) are scaled to data. The individual contributions from pair creation(PC), flavor excitation(FE), and gluon splitting(GS) are drawn in red, green, and blue respectively.

The opening angle for the electron-positron pairs, θ_{ee}^{op} , is shown in Figure 22. Again, peaking in a back-to-back nature, PYTHIA8 observes a more narrow peak than the experimental data. Differing from previous results 16, PYTHIA8 predicts less contributions from flavor excitation compared to PYTHIA6. This is specific to mid-rapidity as this trend was not seen in forward/backward rapidity for the $\mu^+\mu^-$ analysis. The relative contributions from flavor excitation and pair creation are similar, thus leading to a more narrow spectra when compared to the PYTHIA6 results. Furthermore, the presence of gluon splitting here is directly related to the less demanding kinematics for mid-rapidity electron/positron production. The handling matching an merging mechanism, in PYTHIA8 highlights differences in heavy-flavor production mechanisms when probing different phase spaces. Overall, the trends of the PYTHIA8 curves remain relatively consistent to data with some narrowing effect due to the LO/NLO ratio.

4.4 Calculation and Extraction of the Charm Cross Section

The charm cross section serves as an important benchmark for comparing different simulations to experimental findings, allowing us to understand the general precision of these simulations. In this analysis, the charm cross sections were extracted independently for the three analyses that included charm contributions— $\mu\mu$, $e\mu$, and ee .

The procedure of extracting these cross sections began with the full normalization of the three spectra through the branching ratio corrections and acceptance corrections explained in Sections 4.2.3 and 4.3.1, respectively. These absolutely normalized spectra were then scaled to the central values of the experimental data in each channel, resulting in a (central) scaling factor. A slight correction must be made for the $e\mu$ and ee analysis given the presence of both charm and bottom in the signal. Specifically, the bottom cross section was fixed based on the expected ratio of charm to bottom production in 4π , predicted by PYTHIA8. The charm component was then extracted by subtracting the fixed bottom contributions from the total and then scaling accordingly. The effect of this is minimal due to the overall dominance of charm in the spectra alongside the two orders of magnitude difference in cross sections.

The uncertainty of this scaling factor was then calculated for each channel using a data-driven variation approach. The scale factor was recalculated by adjusting the measured data yields to its upper and lower statistical bounds. The difference between these recalculated scaling factors was then used to define the statistical uncertainty of the measurement. To obtain the systematic errors, the same procedure was applied for the systematic bounds. These were done separately for PYTHIA8 generation with and without MPIs and the calculated scaling factors and their respective uncertainties can be found Table 3.

Table 3: Scale factors used in the extraction of charm cross sections for each analysis channel, with and without MPI. Uncertainties are statistical and systematic.

Analysis	MPI	Scale Factor
$\mu\mu$	ON	0.6824 ± 0.0987 (stat) ± 0.0880 syst
	OFF	1.2504 ± 0.1800 (stat) ± 0.1598 syst
$e\mu$	ON	5.0773 ± 2.2840 (stat) ± 2.0764 syst
	OFF	6.5733 ± 2.9083 (stat) ± 2.5947 syst
ee	ON	1.1480 ± 0.1166 (stat) ± 0.3197 syst
	OFF	1.9020 ± 0.1891 (stat) ± 0.5420 syst

To extract the charm production cross section, the scale factors determined from each analysis were then propagated to the PYTHIA8 predicted 4π charm cross section. These serve as a baseline measurement for charm production at the generator level. The charm cross section in 4π , $\sigma_{c\bar{c}}^{4\pi}$, given by PYTHIA8 is $594.7\mu b$ and $356.8\mu b$ for with and without MPIs respectively. The final charm cross sections for each channel were obtained by multiplying the channel-specific scaling factors with these reference values. The resulting cross section measurements can be found in Table 4.

To combine these measurements into a single data-driven cross section, we employed a two-stage approach to separately treat the statistical and systematic uncertainties. The central value of

Table 4: Charm cross section measurements (in μb) for each analysis channel, with and without MPI. Uncertainties are statistical and systematic.

Analysis	MPI	Charm Cross Section [μb]		
$\mu\mu$	ON	$405.81 \pm$	58.67 (stat) \pm	52.35 syst
	OFF	$446.02 \pm$	64.19 (stat) \pm	57.00 syst
$e\mu$	ON	$3019.46 \pm$	1358.31 (stat) \pm	1234.82 syst
	OFF	$2344.71 \pm$	1037.38 (stat) \pm	925.51 syst
ee	ON	$682.71 \pm$	69.32 (stat) \pm	190.13 syst
	OFF	$678.46 \pm$	67.45 (stat) \pm	193.32 syst

the combined charm cross section was computed using a weighted average, where each channel’s contribution was weighted inversely by the square of its statistical uncertainty. This was done to accommodate for the large uncertainties in the $e\mu$ analysis, primarily driven by the substantial uncertainties of the data recordings. This procedure simultaneously calculates the central value and its associated statistical uncertainty through inverse-variance propagation. With this form of calculation, more precise channels (with smaller statistical errors) contribute more significantly to the final average, hence giving a more accurate cross section.

To obtain the systematic uncertainties on the combined cross section, a Monte Carlo-based approach is adopted. The three measurements share a correlated systematic error, driven by the $p + p$ reference cross section. To avoid double counting this error, this was removed from each channel’s systematic uncertainty—effectively reducing each by 10%, in quadrature. Using the remaining uncorrelated component, we construct a Gaussian distribution for each channel centered on the respective measured cross section. The Gaussian distributions were constructed such that the standard deviation, or width, was set to the reduced uncorrelated systematic uncertainty. Thus, in each Monte Carlo trial, a random cross section sample was drawn from its corresponding Gaussian, and then weighted based on the respective statistical uncertainty. Using the statistical inverse-variance weighting method, a single cross section value was determined from the three channel measurements. This was iterated over a large number of trials, to then construct a new Gaussian composed of these cross section measurements. The standard deviation of this Gaussian was extracted to represent the combined uncorrelated systematic uncertainty. Finally, the previously removed 10% correlated systematic uncertainty was added back in quadrature to produce the final combined systematic uncertainty. The combined central values and their respective statistical and systematic uncertainties are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Combined charm production cross sections in p+p collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 200$ GeV, with and without MPI. Results include statistical and systematic uncertainties.

MPI Configuration	Cross Section [μb]
ON	524.09 ± 44.76 (stat) ± 92.66 syst
OFF	560.08 ± 46.45 (stat) ± 104.33 syst

Figure 23 provides a visual summary of the extracted charm cross section across the $\mu\mu$, $e\mu$,

and ee analyses, as well as the combined results with and without MPIs. The data points are shown with their statistical uncertainties (vertical bars) and shaded bands represent the systematic uncertainties. The theoretical predictions from NLO pQCD and PYTHIA8 (with and without MPI) are included as horizontal reference lines. From this plot, we can deduce that the scaled and combined cross sections with and without MPI from PYTHIA fall within theoretical predictions, giving greater confidence of the accuracy of PYTHIA8.

Figure 23: Charm cross section measurements for each analysis channel ($\mu\mu$, $e\mu$, and ee) along with their statistically and systematically combined results (“Combined”), shown with and without multi-parton interactions (MPI). The cross sections are compared to theoretical predictions: the NLO QCD upper and lower bounds (dashed magenta lines) and central prediction (solid magenta), as well as the PYTHIA8 total charm cross section extrapolated to full 4π acceptance with MPI (solid blue) and without MPI (solid red). Vertical bars indicate statistical uncertainties, while shaded bands represent systematic uncertainties.

4.4.1 Comparison of Charm cross Section to Previous Results

The charm cross sections extracted in this analysis give great insight into the accuracy of PYTHIA8 and its ability to represent multiparton interactions. Figure 24 shows a compilation of previously published charm cross section measurements from both the PHENIX and STAR experiments, covering a variety of collision systems at a center-of-mass energy $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200\text{GeV}$. With this analysis, a more complete list of previous measurements was drawn alongside a comparison to the calculated values (from this analysis). These are then compared to the NLO pQCD theoretical bands as well as the PYTHIA8 4π predictions with and without MPI. From this analysis, it is clear that PYTHIA8 performs rather well when observing MPI effects, better measuring the charm cross section and agreeing with other previous measurements. This sheds light on the importance of multiparton interactions at RHIC when modeling charm production. The combined cross sections

calculated from the three dilepton decays channels also serve as a great measurement for the charm cross section. The general consistency within uncertainties suggests that PYTHIA8 can be used to give insight into the heavy-flavor production mechanisms. With the NLO matrix corrections and MPI modeling made in PYTHIA8, we can confidently say that PYTHIA8 serves as a good reliable generator for heavy-flavor studies.

Figure 24: Compilation of total charm production cross section $\sigma_{c\bar{c}}$ at $\sqrt{s} = 200$ GeV from PHENIX and STAR experiments. Black points represent previously published measurements from various collision systems. Error bars represent the statistical uncertainties (red) and systematic uncertainties (blue). The two data points labeled "PYTHIA 8 scaled" correspond to the combined charm cross sections from this analysis (from $\mu\mu$, $e\mu$, and ee channels), using PYTHIA8 4 π scaling with MPI and without MPI. Vertical lines indicate PYTHIA8 full-acceptance predictions and NLO pQCD bounds.

4.5 Calculation and Extraction of the Bottom Cross Section

The bottom cross section was extracted using the like-sign $\mu\mu$ analysis. This was done because other channels (such as unlike-sign ee and $e\mu$) include both charm and bottom components, and are therefore dominated by charm production. To avoid this contamination, we relied exclusively on the like-sign spectra.

The extraction follows a similar scaling procedure used for charm: a scale factor was determined by comparing the PYTHIA8 output with and without MPI to the measured data spectrum. Scaling the PYTHIA8 output to the central data points gave rise to the central scaling factor. Uncertainties were estimated by performing fits to the data's statistical and systematic bounds, providing an upper and lower range for the scale factor.

Upon calculation of this scale factor, it was then propagated to the full 4π PYTHIA8 bottom cross section to obtain the scaled bottom production cross section. Because the PYTHIA generation for this analysis used hard QCD processes, which overestimate the $p+p$ cross section, we effectively scale down the bottom cross section measurements to account for the softQCD:inelastic correction. Specifically, the cross section was rescaled by a factor of $\sigma_{\text{softQCD}}/\sigma_{\text{hardQCD}} \approx 42.0/92.7 \approx 0.453$, to account for the relative probability of bottom production at RHIC parameters. The resulting scale factors and corrected cross sections are summarized in Table 6.

Table 6: Bottom cross section extracted from the like-sign analysis using PYTHIA8 scaling, with and without MPI. The statistical and systematic contributions are , and the final cross section is corrected for the hard-to-soft QCD generation ratio.

Configuration	Scale Factor	Cross Section [μb]
MPI ON	3.78 ± 0.52 (stat) ± 0.23 (syst)	2.50 ± 0.34 (stat) ± 0.15 (syst)
MPI OFF	3.90 ± 0.53 (stat) ± 0.23 (syst)	2.58 ± 0.35 (stat) ± 0.15 (syst)

4.5.1 Comparison of Bottom Cross Section to previous Findings

In Figure 25, we compare our extracted bottom cross sections from the like-sign dimuon analysis to a compilation of prior measurements by PHENIX and STAR, as well as several theoretical models. These include models such as FONLL (fixed-order plus next-to-leading logarithms), MC@NLO and POWHEG (next-to-leading order Monte Carlo generators), and NLO (Vogt) (fixed order predictions based on collinear factorization) [22]. PYTHIA8's 4π prediction is also included in the theory lines, but here as only one line, as PYTHIA predicts the same bottom cross section with and without MPI. The values obtained in this analysis, $\sigma_{b\bar{b}} = 2.50 \pm 0.34, (\text{stat}) \pm 0.15, (\text{syst}) \mu\text{b}$ for with MPI and $2.58 \pm 0.35, (\text{stat}) \pm 0.15, (\text{syst}) \mu\text{b}$ for without MPI are found to lie in good agreement with the broad range of previous experimental results. Although seeming to underestimate the bottom cross section in comparison to other data findings, this may be driven by the broadening of the like-sign dimuon result. In the dimuon result, we found a smearing of the spectra that may have been driven by branching ratio manipulation (see Section 4.3.3). Despite this, the extracted and scaled bottom cross section finding in this analysis do consistently agree with theoretical predictions alongside the experimental findings within uncertainty. This gives great confidence in PYTHIA8's capability to properly analyze heavy-flavor production.

Figure 25: Compilation of $\sigma_{b\bar{b}}$ cross-section measurements at $\sqrt{s} = 200$ GeV in $p + p$ collisions at RHIC, as measured by PHENIX and STAR across various channels. Theoretical predictions from FONLL, MC@NLO, NLO (Vogt), and POWHEG are also shown, along with the PYTHIA8 4π approximation (same for with and without MPI). The final two points correspond to the extracted cross section in this analysis' results (with and without MPI), respectively. Error bars represent statistical uncertainties (red) and total uncertainties (blue).

5 Summary and Outlook

In this analysis, we extracted the integrated charm and bottom cross sections in $p + p$ collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV. This was done using different dilepton decay channels, whilst also analyzing the heavy-flavor production mechanisms that give rise to the respective cross sections. Charm cross sections were obtained for the $\mu\mu$, $e\mu$, and ee channels, each having the respective PYTHIA8 output scale to data yields and then constructing a cross section measurement. Due to the inclusion of bottom decays in the $e\mu$, and ee analyses, the bottom cross section was fixed, such that the charm contribution could be extracted with minimal error. After acquiring the three charm cross sec-

tion measurements, a two-stage approach was utilized to combine the analyses to a singular charm cross section was calculated from PYTHIA8 with and without MPI. The combined cross section of charm was found to $\sigma_{c\bar{c}} = 524.1 \pm 44.8(\text{stat}) \pm 92.7(\text{syst}) \mu\text{b}$ and $560.1 \pm 46.5, (\text{stat}) \pm 104.3, (\text{syst}) \mu\text{b}$ for PYTHIA8 ran with MPI and without MPI respectively. These cross section measurements were then compared to previous charm measurements done at RHIC (at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$), analyzing different collision species. Overall, the cross section measurements were consistent with prior studies alongside the theoretical calculations. This comparison can be found in Figure 24. We further observe that PYTHIA8 measures different cross sections for charm upon tuning the multiparton interactions. This gives rise to the question of their significance.

Highlighting the significance of multiparton interactions at RHIC, PYTHIA8 predicts a more accurate cross section for charm, given the inclusions of MPI. The theoretical predictions from PYTHIA8 with and without MPI are $\sigma_{c\bar{c}} = 594.7 \pm 1.7\mu\text{b}(\text{stat})$ and $356.8 \pm 1.0\mu\text{b}(\text{stat})$ respectively. Observing where these values lie with respect to experimental findings in Figure 24, we can conclude that the simulation software better predicts the 4π charm cross section when MPIs are included. This sheds light on their importance at RHIC energies, despite previous speculation of their little impact. Furthermore, MPIs, within the simulation software serve to improve and correct NLO matrix element calculations to provide a more accurate cross section measurement. Throughout the charm analysis we see some drastic differences in charm yields when comparing the multiparton interaction mode, reinforcing the importance of them.

To close off the analysis we observe the like-sign $\mu\mu$ analysis to calculate the bottom cross section. It is important to utilize this sample as it is unlikely to be contaminated due to the charm and Drell-Yan not contributing to the spectra. When observing correlated pairs, bottom decays are capable of producing like-sign final state leptons due to B^0 meson oscillations. Hence, this provides a clean signal to extract the bottom cross section. Adopting a similar mechanism as in the charm case with some minor corrections (see Section 4.3.3), the bottom cross section from PYTHIA8 with and without MPI were calculated to $\sigma_{b\bar{b}} = 2.50 \pm 0.34(\text{stat}) \pm 0.15(\text{syst}) \mu\text{b}$ and $2.58 \pm 0.35(\text{stat}) \pm 0.15(\text{syst}) \mu\text{b}$ respectively. It is important to note that these values are consistent with one another, solely due to the bottom quark's insensitivity to MPI. Due to the large mass and demanding kinematics for bottom production, it will usually be produced in the hardest process. Thus, this limits its availability in MPIs, particularly at RHIC energies. These measured bottom cross section values were then compared to previous bottom measurements done at RHIC and several theoretical calculations. The bottom cross section was consistent with theoretical predictions and showed overall agreement with previous measurements (see Figure 25).

These findings reassure the accuracy of PYTHIA8 when describing heavy-flavor production at RHIC energies. With the incorporation of the multiparton interaction model in PYTHIA, the accuracies for cumulative cross section measurements have improved from its previous versions. The innovated parton shower modeling and matrix element corrections further reinforce this. The agreement of scaled PYTHIA8 predictions with the shape constructs in the azimuthal angle studies sheds light on its accuracy when observing heavy-flavor production. This gives rise to some confidence in PYTHIA8's capabilities in modeling QCD processes at RHIC energies. Ultimately, this analysis highlights PYTHIA8's value as a probe to observe the relations of heavy quarks that often can be hard to deduce in data.

Moving forward, some studies can further our understanding of the accuracy of the measurements in this study and heavy-flavor modeling. To begin, the results of this study can be compared to other simulation software such as POWHEG and EPOS. This can provide a cross-check with

other Monte Carlo or higher order frameworks. To continue, throughout this study modifications to meson branching ratios were made to provide reasonable statistics. Although these effects were taken into account when normalizing, some doubt is cast on how they may affect the azimuthal angle correlations, specifically discussed in Section 4.3.3.

Moreover the differential cross section outputs from PYTHIA8 can be observe to examine if the measurements at mid-rapidity and forward/backward rapidity agree with experimental findings. This can give some insight as to where inconsistencies may lie and if PYTHIA parameters require some tuning. With emerging studies with the sPHENIX data, PYTHIA8 can further be utilized to observe bottomonium states, particularly the Υ family. As a clean probe for bottom production, PYTHIA8 can give rise to some baseline measurements to observe/compare to data findings. As physicist seek a better understanding of cold nuclear matter effects and bottom production, the Υ meson serves as a great probe. With the sPHENIX experiment, came massive improvements to tracking and calorimetry systems, hence improving track reconstruction and making it possible to resolve individual Upsilon states. With the new data provided with the sPHENIX experiment we can see several avenues open from this form of study, whether in the Quarkonia states or open heavy-flavor production.

6 Appendix

A The PHENIX (Pioneering High Energy Nuclear Interaction eXperiment) experiment

RHIC is home to five key experiments, one of which, the PHENIX experiment. Located at the 8 o'clock direction in the RHIC ring, the PHENIX detector specialized in high-precision measurements of dileptons and direct photons. Some key principles PHENIX was purposed to study were heavy-flavor production mechanisms, quarkonium suppression, and dilepton measurements. To observe collisions, the two beams are steered into the path of the detector via superconducting dipole magnets. Using quadrupole magnets, the beams are further focused to then collide at the interaction point (IP), located at the center of the PHENIX detector. After entering the detector, two main spectrometers, known as the Central Arms and Muon Arms, work in tandem with several other complementary detectors to dissect the collisions and produce sensible data. Figure 26 shows schematic beam and side views for the PHENIX detector highlighting the respective subsystems.

Figure 26: Schematic of the Phenix Detector from the beam view (top) and side view (bottom) in the 2015 run.

A.1 The Central Arms

To begin the discussion of the subsystems, we first observe the properties of the Central Arms. The Central Arms serve to detect photons, electrons, and hadrons at mid-rapidity. Specifically, the Central Arms cover $|\eta| < 0.35$ in rapidity and π in azimuthal. Furthermore, this system is made up of several other detector subsystems to help dissect the interaction plane. These are Silicon Vertex Detectors (VTX), Drift Chambers (DC), PAD Chambers (PC), Ring-Imaging Cherenkov detectors (RICH), Time-Of-Flight detectors (TOF) and Electromagnetic Calorimeters (EMCal). The VTX serves to give precise measurements of the collision vertex whilst distinguishing between charm and bottom decays. This VTX consists of two inner layers, the silicon pixel detectors, and two outer layers, the silicon strip sensors (detectors). These layers can be seen in the VTX schematic

provided in Figure 27. The VTX uses these layers to track the distances between the primary vertex and the decay vertex. Using this output, the decay length can be measured such that we can distinguish between charmed and bottom decays. It is important to note that D mesons innately have much shorter decays than B meson. These measurements are further improved with the use of the drift chambers and PAD chambers. In particular, the DC and PC work together with the central magnet to determine the momentum of charged particles by measuring the angle of a particle's trajectory in the magnetic field [9]. This in turn produces better tracking and event reconstruction.

The RICH and TOF detectors are primarily used for particle identification. The RICH detector uses the Cherenkov effect to identify electron and positrons, separating them from hadrons. This effect occurs when a charged particle moves faster than the speed of light in a medium, it emits Cherenkov radiation in the form of a cone of light. This ring of light depends on the velocity of the particle and, due to the lower mass of electrons and positrons, one can easily distinguish the radiation patterns from much, heavier hadrons. The TOF detector serves to measure the time it took for a particle to travel from the collision point to the detector. This serves to separate signals from hadrons such as pions and kaons. Lastly, the EM calorimeter, made up of lead-scintillator (PbSc) and lead-glass (PbGl) modules, serves to measure the energy of photons and electrons via electromagnetic showers.

Figure 27: Cross sectional view of the VTX detector showing the relative positions of individual layers B0, B1, B2, and B3 from smallest to largest radius.

A.2 The Muon Arms

The muon arms are positioned at the backward and forward rapidities, covering the rapidity ranges of $-2.2 < |\eta| < -1.2$ and $1.2 < |\eta| < 2.4$ for the south and north arm, respectively. Furthermore, the Muon Arms have a coverage of 2π in azimuth. The Muon Arms serve to record muons and their properties, but due to the absorbers present, some measurements of charged hadrons can also be made. These muon arms consist of a forward Silicon Vertex Detector (FVTX), Muon Trackers (MuTr), and Muon Identifiers (MuID). Similarly to the VTX, the FVTX records the hits of charged particles, allowing for track reconstruction and decay length analysis. This allows us to distinguish muons coming from charmed decays from bottom decays.

A.2.1 Muon Tracker (MuTr)

The Muon Tracker was designed to measure the momentum of muons before exiting the absorber material. Using the South and North Arm Magnets, one could draw conclusions on the momentum of an incoming muon based on the bending in its trajectory. The Muon Trackers can be broken down into three tracking "stations", positioned at 1.8, 3.0, 4.6 m and 1.8, 3.47, 6.12 m from the origin of the south and north, respectively [23]. These three tracking stations consist of multi-layered cathode strip chambers (CSCs), denoted as stations 1, 2, and 3, from the collision point outward. Station 1 is divided into quadrants (4 segments) azimuthally and is comprised of 3 layers along the z direction. Following the same formalism, station 2 is divided into octants (8 segments) and consists of 3 layers, whilst station 3 is divided into octants and consists of 2 layers. The orientation of these CSCs can be seen in Figure 28. Between the cathode layers, which run radially, an anode wire is placed between them, filling the "gap," such that they are perpendicular to the cathode, forming the chamber. These chambers are filled with a gas mixture composed of 50% Ar, 30% CO₂, and 20% CF₄. It is important to note that these cathode strips lie in what is considered the cathode plane, and with each proceeding cathode plane, a small angle is differed, to identify the radial position of the particle (stereo plane). This angle variation can be seen in Figure 30, where the stereo planes differ in each gap, hence eliminating ghost tracks.

Figure 28: Muon Tracking nomenclature [23].

Figure 29: A schematic of the south muon magnet and muon tracking stations [23].

Figure 30: A drawing of different gaps in the MuTr. The orientation of the stereo planes are different for each gap to eliminate ghost hits [23].

The Muon Magnets serve to assist in the momentum measurement in the MuTr. The Muon Magnets are two 10 meter tall solenoidal magnets placed in the north and south arms. These produce a radial magnetic field such that the $\oint \mathbf{B} \cdot d\mathbf{l}$ line, 15 degrees from the beam axis are 0.72 and 0.75 Tesla-meters for the north and south magnets respectively[9]. One can observe a charged particle's interaction with this field via the perpendicular component of its velocity, which is affected by the Lorentz force. Hence, by observing the bending angle, the momentum of the particle of the particle can be extracted allowing for a better understanding of the final-state muons.

Figure 31: Magnetic field lines for the two Central Magnet coils in combined (++) mode [23].

A.2.2 Muon Identifier (MuID)

The Muon Identifier (MuID), located behind the MuTr, is comprised of 5 alternating layers. These layers consist of thick steel absorbers and Iarocci tube-based tracking detectors. These layers serve to distinguish muons from hadronic background. Hadronic background is often caught or absorbed in the steel absorbers as muons penetrate the layers. The MuID distinguishes muon candidates from hadrons by requiring the incident particle to penetrate to the 4th or last layer of the MuID. It is important to note that since the MuID is placed outside the magnetic field of the Muon Magnets, particles will travel in a straight line through the MuID. The MuID is built such that in the gaps between layers one can find two planes with 6 overlapping panels in each. These are oriented such that one is placed vertically and one horizontally. This orientation can be seen in Figure 32. Within each of the detection planes, an array of Iarocci tubes are arranged in staggered two-packs to increase the efficiency and avoid gaps in detection. A cross-sectional view of the MuID panels and Iarocci tubes can be seen in Figure 33. As muons traverse the MuID, they ionize the CO_2 and isobutane gas within the Iarocci tubes, leaving behind a signal to reconstruct their respective tracks.

Figure 32: A drawing of a MuID gap [23].

Cross section of the MuID panel

Cross section of the plastic tube(2-pack)

Figure 33: A drawing of the Iarocci tubes [23].

A.2.3 Absorbers

Alongside the hadron absorbers built into the MuID and MuTr, some pre-MuTr absorbers exist to reject more hadrons before entering the detection systems. To begin, the Central Magnet and the 20 cm-thick copper nose cones (on the central magnet) serve to absorb hadrons and generate a cleaner signal in the muon arms. Furthermore, in 2012, 35 cm-thick stainless steel absorbers were installed on the outside surface of the Central Magnets to further absorb hadrons. A summary of all hadron absorbers and their respective thicknesses and interaction lengths are given in Table 7. The effective interaction length, $\lambda_I/\cos\theta$. Here, λ_I is the nuclear interaction length, which measures how far a high-energy hadron can travel in a material before undergoing a nuclear interaction. This varies based on the material density and atomic properties. Furthermore, θ , represents the angle of incidence for a particle relative to the absorber. This construction of absorbers seeks to efficiently clean out the muon signal. As hadrons and electrons interact electromagnetically with the materials, they are absorbed, leaving behind the weakly interacting muons.

Table 7: List of hadron absorbers and their thickness in the Muon Arms. The values are given for the South (North) arms respectively [9].

Absorber	Material	Thickness (cm)	$\lambda_I/\cos\theta$
Nose cone	Copper	20 (20)	1.8 (1.8)
Central Magnet	Steel	60 (60)	3.1 (3.1)
Stainless steel absorbers	Stainless Steel	35 (35)	2.2 (2.2)
Sum of pre-MuTr	-	115 (115)	7.1 (7.1)
Muon Magnet yoke	Steel	20 (30)	1.1 (1.5)
MuID 1st Layer	Steel	10 (10)	0.6 (0.6)
MuID 2nd Layer	Steel	10 (10)	0.6 (0.6)
MuID 3rd Layer	Steel	20 (20)	1.2 (1.2)
MuID 4th Layer	Steel	20 (20)	1.2 (1.2)
MuID 5th Layer	Steel	20 (20)	1.2 (1.2)
Sum of post-MuTr	-	100 (110)	5.9 (6.3)
Total	-	215 (225)	13.0 (13.4)

A.3 Muon Piston Calorimeters (MPC)

The Muon Piston Calorimeters cover $3.1 < |\eta| < 3.7$ in rapidity and have a 2π azimuthal coverage. The MPC uses lead-tungstate (PbWO_4) crystal calorimeters to absorb electromagnetic showers. The MPC's main purpose is to measure π^0 and η mesons. The MPC was then improved in 2015, when the Muon Piston Calorimeter Extension (MPC-EX) was added, serving to provide increased precision in separating the prompt photons from the π^0 hadrons. This improvement helped probe the low Bjorken-x region.

A.4 Global Detectors

The global detectors, more specifically, the Beam Beam Counters (BBC) and the Zero Degree Calorimeters (ZDC) are key when measuring collision centrality, event timing, and initial kinematics. The BBC is positioned in the far-forward and backward rapidity regions ($3.0 < |\eta| < 3.9$) and its main role is to provide local level-1 triggers by requiring a "hit" or signal in both the north and south detectors. The two arms of the BBC consist of 64 quartz Cherenkov counters oriented in three layers. These Cherenkov counters produce Cherenkov light when struck by a charged particle, thus leading into a photomultiplier where the light is converted into electrical signals. By analyzing the time difference between these signals, or hits, the collision vertex, or z_{vtx} can be determined. Using the relationships between the timing of hits at each arm, the location of z_{vtx} , and the fact that the BBC detects particles with velocities $v > 0.7c$, we can derive the following relations:

$$z_{vtx} = \frac{(T_S - T_N) \cdot c}{2}, \quad (14)$$

$$T_0 = \frac{T_S + T_N}{2} - \frac{L}{c}, \quad (15)$$

In the above, T_S and T_N are the average times of charged particles hitting the north and south BBC respectively[9]. The distance from the interaction point to each BBC is represented by L , while T_0 is the time of the collision. These measurements are analogous to the illustration in Figure 34.

Figure 34: An illustration of the measurement of the z vertex position [24].

The ZDC serves as a hadron calorimeter, using a tungsten absorber to induce hadronic showers. The ZDC is positioned downstream the DX dipole magnets, where charged particles are deflected by the field and only neutral spectator neutrons reach the detector. Minimizing the background contamination via the dipole magnets allows the ZDC to count spectator neutrons to gain a better understanding of the centrality of the collision. The number of neutrons is inversely proportional to the collision centrality, where many spectator neutrons point to peripheral collision and vice versa. Furthermore, the ZDC also provides a local level-1 trigger, requiring hits in both the south and north detectors.

A.5 Data Acquisition

The Data Acquisition (DAQ) system in PHENIX was responsible for handling the large volume of data produced by the detector subsystems[25]. The DAQ collects raw data from all detector subsystems and applies triggers to determine acceptable events to record. An example of these

triggers are shown from the Run15 $p + p$ collisions in Table 8. It is important to note that these triggers varied based on the collision species being observed. Heav-ion collision will innately have a much higher collision rate, on the order of a few kHz, while $p+p$ collision will have collision rates on the order of a few MHz. The DAQ employs a multi-event buffering system (MEB) that allows it to receive, process, and transmit data all in parallel. This MEB system allows for the processing of multiple events simultaneously, preventing bottleneck and reducing the dead time. Furthermore, the DAQ also implements a complex triggering system to assist in handling data from subsystems. These triggers can be separated into 3 categories, the level-1 (L1) triggers, level-2 (L2) triggers, and level-3 (L3) triggers. The L1 triggers use fast detector signals, such as those coming from the BBC, ZDC, and EMCal. These often record triggers on the order of a few microseconds. The L2 triggers are more complex in that they come with the processing of data and advanced selection criteria. These triggers can take anywhere around a few hundreds of microseconds. L3 triggers come with full event reconstruction and are fully software based. These can use full tracking and calorimeter clustering to record the triggers, These triggers can occur on the order of a few milliseconds. An illustration of the DAQ system can be seen in Figure 35.

Figure 35: An illustration of the PHENIX DAQ system [25].

Table 8: List of triggers used in the Run15 $p + p$ collisions

Name	Scale Down	Livetime
BBCLL1(> 0 tubes)	2749	0.91
BBCLL1(> 0 tubes) novertex	4949	0.91
ZDCCLL1wide	97	0.92
BBCLL1(noVtx)&(ZDCN ZDCS)	225	0.92
BBCLL1(> 0 tubes) narrowvtx	12	0.91
ZDCNS	97	0.91
ERT_4x4b	0	0.83
ERT_4x4a&BBCLL1	0	0.93
ERT_4x4c&BBCLL1	0	0.93
ERTLL1_E&BBCLL1(narrow)	0	0.92
FVTX_HighMult_N	9999999	0.00
FVTX_HighMult_S	9999999	0.00
MPC_N_S_A	0	0.89
MPC_S_B	0	0.90
MPC_S_C&ERT_2x2	0	0.92
MPC_S_C&MPC_S_C	0	0.91
CLOCK	196077	0.91
MPC_N_B	0	0.87
MPC_N_C&ERT_2x2	0	0.92
MPC_N_C&MPC_N_C	0	0.16
MUIDLL1_N2D&BBCLL1novtx	0	0.77
MUIDLL1_S2D&BBCLL1novtx	0	0.81
MUIDLL1_N1D&BBCLL1novtx	1	0.91
MUIDLL1_S1D&BBCLL1novtx	0	0.90
MUON_N_SG3&MUIDLL1_(1D 1H) &BBCLL1novtx(nppg)	0	0.91
MUON_S_SG3&MUIDLL1_(1D 1H) &BBCLL1novtx(nppg)	0	0.91
MUON_N_SG3&BBCLL1novtx(nppg)	122	0.92
MUON_S_SG3&BBCLL1novtx(nppg)	15	0.92
PPG(Pedestal)	0	0.93
PPG(Test Pulse)	0	0.92
PPG(Laser)	0	0.93
Noise	0	0.00

B The sPHENIX Experiment

After the conclusion of the PHENIX experiment in 2016, the detector was modified and upgraded to form the sPHENIX detector. The innovations of the detector sought to provide improved jet reconstructions and insight into the Upsilon mass region. sPHENIX came with several upgrades, including the Monolithic Active Pixel Vertex Detector (MVTX), the Time Projection Chamber (TPC), and (Hadronic and Electromagnetic) calorimeter upgrades. Furthermore, these enhancements were met with the introduction of a much stronger 1.5 T solenoid magnet to improve tracking of charged particles and more precise momentum resolution. A schematic view of the sPHENIX detector can be seen in Figures 36 and 42. Overall, the sPHENIX detector served to improve the understanding of QGP dynamics, heavy flavor and quarkonia studies, and jet substructure and fragmentation studies. In the following sections, the significant innovations to the detector will be discussed.

Figure 36: Schematic diagram of the sPHENIX detector including all of its subsystems [26].

B.1 Monolithic Active Pixel Vertex Detector (MVTX)

The Monolithic Active Pixel Detector (MVTX) is the innermost tracking component of the many tracking detectors present in the sPHENIX detector. Inspired by the ALICE Inner Tracking System (ITS) used at CERN, the MVTX is made up of 48 staves oriented into three layers. These layers are spaced such that the first layer is closest to the beam pipe ($r \sim 2.3$ cm), the second layer, or intermediate layer lies above this ($r \sim 3.2$ cm), and the outer layer is farthest from the beam pipe ($r \sim 4.0$ cm). The sensor technology implemented by the MVTX is well described by the Monolithic Active Pixel Sensors (MAPS), which utilize nine ALICE Pixel Detectors (ALPIDE) chips. This MAPS technology allows for much more precise spatial resolutions ($\sim 5 \mu\text{m}$) [27]. This form of sensor technology allows for much cleaner readout for the Front-End Link eXchange (FELIX) board, hence providing the capabilities for continuous streaming readout. A 3D rendering of the MVTX can be seen (in blue) in Figure 37, where the Intermediate Silicon Strip Tracker (INTT) can be seen as the larger, green layers.

The MVTX surpasses its predecessor, the VTX, in that it encompasses a 2π azimuthal coverage and provides much more precise measurements of primary and decay vertices. This is driven by

the differences in pixel size and spacial resolution; where the MVTX has a pixel size and spacial resolution of $\sim 5 \mu\text{m}$ and $\sim 5 \mu\text{m}$ respectively and the VTX has a pixel size and spacial resolution $\sim 50 \mu\text{m}$ and $\sim 30 \mu\text{m}$ respectively[27]. These precisions allow for cleaner separation of B and D meson decays for heavy flavor studies alongside the separation of prompt and non-prompt J/ψ production for quarkonia studies.

Figure 37: A 3D rendering of the sPHENIX silicon detectors as implemented in ACTS. The small blue layers are the MVTX, and the large green layers are the INTT. [27].

B.2 Intermediate Silicon Strip Tracker (INTT)

Another key component of the sPHENIX tracking systems is the Intermediate Silicon Strip Tracker (INTT). The INTT serves to provide precision tracking of charged particles in the central rapidity region, bridging the gap between the MVTX and the Time Projection Chamber (TPC). The INTT consists of two cylindrical layers of silicon strip detectors, forming the intermediate tracking layer between the MVTX and TPC. These two layers are comprised of 56 silicon ladders, 24 in the inner barrel, and 32 in the outer barrel. Within these layers, the ladders are staggered to ensure a seamless and full azimuthal coverage. A 3D rendering of these layers is shown in Figure 37 in green. These ladders are further broken down into two types of silicon strip sensors, both with a strip pitch of $78 \mu\text{m}$ and thickness of $320 \mu\text{m}$. These Type-A and Type-B sensors provide precise tracking in the intermediate region allowing for better matching between tracking detectors. The

specifications of the two types of sensors can be found in Table 9 and a picture of the INNT ladders can be found in Figure 38. It is key to recognize that the INNT served to replace and improve upon the FVTX present in the PHENIX experiment, allowing for a full acceptance tracking system.

Table 9: The dimensions of type-A and type-B silicon strip sensors [28].

Type	# of blocks	active area dimension	strip pitch
A	16	128 mm × 19.96 mm	78 μm
B	8	100 mm × 19.96 mm	78 μm

Figure 38: A photo of the INNT ladder with sensors facing up. Here, the HDIs are the high-density interconnects, serving as a read out for 13 FPHX chips on each respective half. These chips handle the signal processing and digitization of information [28].

B.3 Time Projection Chamber (TPC)

The Time Projection Chamber serves as the primary tracking detector for the sPHENIX experiment, playing a critical role in the reconstruction of charged-particle trajectories and the clustering of jets. The TPC has a radial coverage of $20\text{cm} < r < 78\text{cm}$, a rapidity coverage of $|\eta| < 1.1$, and a full 2π azimuthal coverage[29]. Originally inspired by the ALICE and STAR experiments' TPC designs, the sPHENIX TPC features an optimized design for improved spatial and time resolutions, making it well suited for heavy-ion collisions.

Figure 39: Quad-GEM Configuration from ALICE Technical Design Report (TDC) [30].

Replacing the Drift and Pad Chambers of the PHENIX experiment, the TPC utilizes a 1.4T solenoidal magnetic field to bend charged particle trajectories to extract observables such as momentum and track path. Originally designed to use Ne-CF₄ gas mixture, the TPC gas was later changed to isobutane, to enhance drift stability and reduce ion backflow[31]. The key innovation of the TPC is its Quadruple-GEM (Gas Electron Multiplier) readout system. These Quad-GEMs

amplify ionized electrons while suppressing ion backflow, thus reducing space charge distortions and enabling continuous and ungated readout. This is ideal for heavy ion collisions, allowing for precise measurements despite the high frequency of events. The quad-GEM configuration can be seen in Figure 39 from the ALICE TDC. The TPC also features readout pads oriented in a zigzag pattern to promote charge sharing between pads. In turn, we can achieve better reconstruction of the location of charge clouds in the TPC. This is modeled in Figure 40 below.

Figure 40: Simulation of Zigzag Segmented Pads, A) Three clouds of charge dropped from 2mm above pads. B) Charge density at pad level. C) Charge distribution resulting from a plane of uniform charge [29].

B.4 Hadron Calorimeter (HCal) and other Calorimetry Improvements

With the sPHENIX experiment, came significant upgrades to the calorimetry. Particularly, PHENIX struggled with jet reconstruction due to its lack of a dedicated Hadron Calorimeter (HCal). The PHENIX calorimeters were restricted to $|\eta| < 0.35$, but with new dedicated HCal, the rapidity coverage was extended to $|\eta| < 1.1$. The HCal is divided into two sections, the inner (iHCal) and outer (oHCal) sections, where the iHCal is located inside the BaBar (1.4 T solenoidal magnet) to provide pre-shower detection and the oHCal is located outside the solenoid to ensure full hadronic energy containment. This orientation can be seen in the mock schematic in Figure 41. Each HCal segment features tilted steel absorber plates and plastic scintillators in an alternating fashion. The absorber plates are tapered and tilted, with respect to the radial direction, to provide more uniform sampling in the azimuth. To continue, the plastic scintillators are embedded with wavelength shifting (WLS) fibers that serve to collect light. As hadronic showers deposit energy in the scintillator tiles, the produced light is collected by these WSL fibers and then readout by silicon photomultiplier (SiPM). It is important to note that the inner and outer HCal are tilted in opposite directions, and this is done to ensure uniform energy deposition in the HCal (shown in Figure 41).

The EMCal also experienced some major improvements with the start of the sPHENIX experi-

ment. To begin, the lead-based absorbers were replaced with tungsten-based absorbers, which with the higher density allow for a more compact calorimeter and reduction in fluctuations in shower energy measurements. Furthermore, the lead-based scintillators in the original EMCal were replaced with scintillating fibers (SciFi), which are embedded in a matrix of tungsten powder and epoxy (W/SciFi) [32]. With this "Spaghetti" Calorimeter (SPACAL) Design, a much finer segmentation was achieved, thus improving shower shape identification. The effective efficiency of light collection was improved with these innovations, alongside the energy resolution and timing performance. With these improvements to the Calorimeter subsystems came some key capabilities: full jet reconstruction, precise partonic energy loss measurements in the QGP, differentiation between quark- and gluon-initiated jets, and heavy-flavor jet tagging.

Figure 41: Schematic diagram of the beam test setup. From left to right, it includes the EMCal, inner HCal, mock cryostat, and outer HCal prototypes [32].

Figure 42: Rendering of the sPHENIX Detector with section cut-away. sEPD and MBD are not shown but would exist near the end caps of the barrel [33].

With the emergence of the sPHENIX experiment, many doors were opened in high-energy physics and QGP studies. These new capabilities allowed for higher precision measurements of jets, heavy-flavor and quarkonia. It is key to recognize the enhancements made to the PHENIX detector as well as the respective strengths of both detectors. In this thesis, PHENIX data was utilized from Run15, to perform an angular correlation study on heavy-flavor production using dilepton measurements. With the innovations to simulation softwares, physicists were keen to understand how accurate these generators can explain experimental findings.

6 Bibliography

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